

IE UNIVERSIDAD

TESIS DOCTORAL / DOCTORAL DISSERTATION

“UNA PERSPECTIVA ORGANIZACIONAL
MULTINIVEL SOBRE EL PAPEL DE LA SEDE
CENTRAL EN LA COLABORACIÓN ENTRE
UNIDADES”

“A MULTI-LEVEL ORGANIZATIONAL
PERSPECTIVE ON THE ROLE OF HQ IN
CROSS-UNIT COLLABORATION”

Jeremy M. Nurse

SEGOVIA, 2023

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ABSTRACT

How complex corporations with multidimensional structures create value is a topic of enduring interest and relevance. What is missing from the published literature are in-depth examinations of the nuances found in complex corporate structures, their vertical layers, and particularly with respect to multi-level headquarters (HQ) structures. To fill this gap, this dissertation presents the analysis of a multiple case study in the Massy Group, a large multidivisional, and multinational corporation that operates in the Caribbean, Latin America, and the United States. My research focuses specifically on how corporate parents seek to create value, particularly in relation to how organizational integration is sought in complex corporate structures. Through in-depth interviews with a total of 55 Massy Group insiders as informants across five strategic initiatives that involved different kinds of cross-unit collaboration, I sought insight into two research questions: 1) What is the role of multiple HQ levels in supporting cross-unit collaboration? and 2) How do multiple HQ levels deploy integrative devices to support cross-unit collaboration? In my research, I concluded that both management and oversight at multiple HQ levels are crucial for enabling cross-unit collaboration and elaborated on how the theoretical concepts of integrative devices can manifest as HQ roles. More specifically, the study highlighted how the use of authority, communication, and cross-unit structure are important integrative devices that support collaboration within this organizational context. Overall, the findings of this research contribute to a better understanding of the roles and mechanisms through which multiple HQ levels can facilitate cross-unit collaboration in a large, diversified multinational firms.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
CHQ	Corporate Headquarters
DHQ	Divisional Headquarters
DOB	Distribution Own Brands
e.g.	exempli gratia (for example)
ERB	Exclusive Retail Brands
EVP	Executive Vice President
FY	Financial Year
HQ	Headquarters
HR	Human Resources
HSSE	Health, Safety, Security & Environment
ID	Integrative Device
i.e.	id est (that is)
IT	Information Technology
ITC	Information Technology & Communications
M&A	Mergers & Acquisitions
OHQ	Operating Company Headquarters
OSHA	Occupational Safety and Health Administration
SVP	Senior Vice President

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

To my wife Zyreene – thank you kindly for having an infinite amount of patience throughout this seemingly interminable journey of completing my doctoral dissertation. I could not have done this without you and words cannot express how eternally grateful I am to have you as my partner. Love always and thank you!

To my Mother, Father, and Sister – while I never took the time to discuss in any material way the intricacies associated with my research, you were always there to support me from inception on this doctoral program. Throughout my entire life, you continuously encouraged me to pursue my dreams and to think abundantly. Thank you for this gift!

To my Research Assistants Sanella and Amit – you both are great friends who committed time and effort to provide much needed support at various junctures in my project over the years. I have been working on my research for so long that you probably thought that I forgot you, but that would be impossible given your amazing contributions in helping me pull this off. Thank you!

To my Doctoral Advisor Mikko Ketokivi – simply put, you are one of the best advisors that a doctoral student can have. I know that you had to be extremely patient with me given my continuously increasing responsibilities, commitments, and promotions at work, which often affected my ideal timelines. However, your astute guidance and support combined with practical insights, ultimately allowed me to deliver a final product that I certainly am proud of. Thank you!

To Massy - I would like to personally thank all the informants who agreed to be interviewed as the rich information elicited from these discussions in 2019 and 2020 provided the foundation that allowed me to make my academic contribution. I would like to specifically acknowledge Gervase Warner (President & Group Chief Executive Officer), Frere Delmas (Retired Executive Vice President) and Earl Boodasingh (Retired Executive Vice President), all who mentored me at different stages of my career within Massy while I conducted this study. I am extremely appreciative for the sponsorship and endorsement of my research agenda which has helped me not only to be a better researcher, but also to be a better executive with an enhanced understanding 'how' things happen in the underbelly of such a large complex organization. Thank you, thank you, thank you!

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Background Context & Motivation

In the academic literature, there is already a substantial body of knowledge on the role of headquarters (HQ) in studies on corporate strategy (Campbell, Goold & Alexander, 1995; Collis & Montgomery, 1998) and organization design (Goold & Campbell, 2002a; Galbraith, 2014). This solid theoretical background has provided us with a great understanding of how large firms manage their respective business segments or divisions across multiple geographic markets. However, from my review of the literature, it appears that the notion of corporate parenting (Goold, Campbell & Alexander, 1994) has somewhat been trivialized in organizational research, oftentimes not providing an adequate picture of the inherent characteristic of having multiple levels of HQs, particularly in a complex corporate structure.

I recognize that studies have been undertaken which acknowledge the existence of HQs at different levels in large firms (Alfoldi, Clegg & McGaughey, 2012; Manke et al., 2012), but the need to deepen our comprehension of the roles these different HQ levels play is needed (Menz, Kunisch & Collis, 2015). The intellectual roots on the functions, operations, relations, and significance of HQ have traditionally been ascribed from research on multibusiness and multinational firms (Menz, Kunisch & Collis, 2015). Therefore, I suspect that these same roots and institutionalized positioning of studies on HQ naturally focus the attention of researchers on *product, service line, business, or division* and *national, regional, or geographic* dimensions of large corporate organizations. This may have given rise to an oversight that resulted in many

scholars not taking the *vertical* dimension comparatively seriously with respect to the role of HQ.

From the literature, we also know that there is ample evidence that firms seek to create value through collaboration and integration amongst its organizational sub-units, or simply cross-unit collaboration (Goold & Campbell, 1998; Graebner, 2004; Helfat & Eisenhardt, 2004; Castañer & Ketokivi, 2018). Nevertheless, while we know that it is possible for firms to create value from cross-unit collaboration, gaining a greater understanding into how they undertake and achieve such activities is still very important, which has not been largely as forthcoming in the literature (Martin & Eisenhardt, 2010).

Therefore, the oversight mentioned above enlarges, when one tries to intersect and understand what roles multiple HQ levels play specifically in organizational activities that involve cross-unit collaboration within complex corporate structures. Fundamentally, the above opportunities to deepen our insight into the underbelly of corporations that host multiple HQ levels, have served to fuel my interest in conducting this research. Hence, I see my job as putting forth a contribution which satisfactorily addresses this oversight, and I am hopeful that it will encourage more researchers to conduct future empirical studies on the multi-level HQ organizational phenomenon.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this multiple case study was to directly engage with several key executives, managers, and officers within a large firm to elicit their perspectives on the role that multiple HQ levels play in cross-unit collaboration, as well as to

understand how the respective HQ levels utilize specific integrative devices to enact such cross-unit collaboration. It is anticipated that improving our understanding of how large multinational firms with heterogeneous portfolios function with several HQ levels will help to enhance the design of these types of organizations.

The main objective was to answer the two following research questions:

1. What is the role of multiple HQ levels in supporting cross-unit collaboration?
2. How do multiple HQ levels deploy integrative devices to support cross-unit collaboration?

Research Approach

My research is seeking to address the oversight and research questions above, building on existing theoretical foundations on the role of HQ and organizational integration. Therefore, the research approach encompassed a multiple case study structured to support the elaboration of theory (Ketokivi & Choi, 2014). The study was conducted inside the Massy Group of Companies (Massy, in short), a large diversified multinational corporation operating in the Caribbean, Latin America, and the US. The firm also has multiple organizational levels and HQ layers, and can be characterized as a multinational, multibusiness and a multi-level firm. I provide more background information on Massy in Chapter Three.

As I was investigating the role of multiple HQ levels in cross-unit collaboration, I identified five cases within this research setting that were characterized by the

involvement of different HQ levels in strategic initiatives which entailed cross-unit collaboration. I selected 55 key informants from different HQ levels based on their participation and understanding of the initiatives, and thereafter conducted interviews with these informants. Field notes developed from the interviews provided the primary source of data and information collected. Secondary data sources such as public filings and internal company documents were also utilized. The data collected from the interviews was coded and appropriately organized in a manner which facilitated the case analysis. The data was subsequently analyzed using various techniques to extract findings to support overall theory elaboration and the empirical contribution.

The Researcher

At the time of conducting the study, my role was that of an insider researcher being an executive employed within the case study organization. More specifically, at the time of completing this dissertation, I held the position of Senior Vice President, Corporate Strategy & Transactions for Massy and I have included my professional biography in Appendix C. While there are several advantages to being an insider researcher, I also acknowledge the biases and shortcomings that can arise by being in this position (Morey & Luthans, 1984). Considering this, I have included some self-reflections as an insider researcher to be as transparent as possible in presenting my research. Additionally, I utilized techniques such as triangulation via multiple data sources, and I applied peer reviews and inter-rater reliability checks (Bloomberg & Volpe, 2016) in collaboration with my doctoral advisor to strengthen the credibility of my research.

Manuscript Structure

The remaining sections of this dissertation are organized as follows. Chapter Two provides a review of the literature establishing the theoretical background and positioning of my research which falls within the intersection between parenting as it relates to the role of HQ, and organizational integration with respect to cross-unit collaboration. Chapter Three follows with details on the overall research methodology, including the research design, research setting, case selection, key informant selection, data collection, coding, issues of trustworthiness and ethical considerations.

Chapter Four starts by providing case study organization contextual insights on the role of HQ, then goes into the findings and corresponding interpretations both within each case, as well as across the cases. Chapter Five presents the conclusions and main contributions from the study. I also put forth my perspective on directions for future research based on the limitations appertaining to this study as well as opportunities for further contributions, and then I end the chapter with my final reflections.

Table 1.1: Main Body Manuscript Structure

CHAPTER LABEL	CHAPTER TITLE
CHAPTER ONE	INTRODUCTION
CHAPTER TWO	LITERATURE REVIEW
CHAPTER THREE	RESEARCH METHODOLOGY
CHAPTER FOUR	FINDINGS & INTERPRETATION
CHAPTER FIVE	DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

Definitions of Key Terminology

Unit: A unit is defined in relation to the specific context, and may refer to a business unit, line of business, subsidiary, operating company, function, or department within a large corporation. In this dissertation, the terms unit and subunit are used interchangeably.

Cross-Unit Collaboration: Integrative activity exhibited by multiple units within a large corporation based on the intention to create economic value (Martin & Eisenhardt, 2010). Cross-unit collaboration may take various forms and have different objectives depending on the nature of the integration challenge and units involved in the initiative.

Integrative Device: A set of tools or mechanisms in which management of a firm deploys to achieve organizational integration of some form (Castañer & Ketokivi, 2018).

CHQ: An acronym that represents the Corporate Headquarters, which is the most central organizational unit of a large corporation (Menz, Kunisch & Collis, 2015).

DHQ: An acronym that represents the Divisional Headquarters, which is a lower-level central organizational unit responsible for a subunit or a cluster of units within a large corporation.

OHQ: An acronym that represents the Operating Company Headquarters, which is the lowest level central organizational unit responsible for an operating company or subsidiary of a large corporation.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

The purpose of this multiple case study is to enhance our understanding of the roles which different HQ levels play in cross-unit collaboration, and how they go about achieving this. To legitimately carry out this study, it was necessary to perform a critical evaluation of the literature related to the research topic, which is included in this chapter. I have organized the chapter starting with this brief introduction, followed by two sub-sections that present detailed literature reviews on corporate parenting and organizational integration respectively. To conclude, I provide a synthesis of the key points covered in the overall chapter.

It is important to elaborate on the reasons why I identified these two major areas of literature for critical examination. Firstly, research on the various roles of HQ has accessed several organizational theories and fields including but not limited to structural contingency theory (Chandler, 1962), the resource-based view of the firm (Wernerfelt, 1984) and corporate strategy (Porter, 1987; Collis, Young & Goold, 2007). However, the dominant theoretical perspectives on parenting in relation to the functioning of HQ distinctly focus on it as a value-additive entity (Campbell, Goold & Alexander, 1995a; Goold & Campbell, 2002a). Therefore, given that my research is about enhancing knowledge on the roles multiple HQ levels play in cross-unit collaboration, as intentional value-creating activities, then it seems reasonable for this assessment to be done through the lens of corporate parenting.

Secondly, as it relates to improving our comprehension of how multiple HQ levels effectuate cross-unit collaboration, I leveraged theoretical ideas and concepts from the organizational integration literature. More specifically, I focused on *integrative devices*, as they can provide pathways to achieving integration (Castañer & Ketokivi, 2018). I have positioned cross-unit collaboration, as defined in this study, as a subset of broader organizational integration themes that involve interactions between organizational subunits within the context of large corporations.

Before proceeding to the next section, I would like to share a few other considerations which helped to shape the content embedded in this chapter. The first is that throughout my research process, the literature was continuously reviewed as different concepts emerged from the data collected and analyses conducted. This iterative approach to scouring the literature is not uncommon, particularly in case study research (Bloomberg & Volpe, 2016). Secondly, my research contribution lies within the intersection of parenting and organizational integration, and therefore I have created a theoretical positioning framework (see Figure 2.1 below) which is representative of this viewpoint.

Also, my study involves the derivation of real-world insights, on the roles that multiple HQ levels play in cross-unit collaboration and how they attain it, from various case studies embedded within one large corporation. Although these insights were accumulated from a specific organizational context, they can still provide and support the elaboration of existing theories for future analytical generalization (Ketokivi & Choi, 2014).

Figure 2.1: Theoretical Positioning Framework

Source: Author's analysis

Corporate Parenting and The Role of HQ

In this section, I pay homage to the substantial contributions that have been made on parenting and the role of HQ as an organizational unit. I specifically recognize the work done on the definitions of corporate parenting, then I elaborate on the theoretical foundations on HQ by leveraging the rich plethora of research already undertaken on multibusiness and multinational firms. Additionally, I delve into the extant perspectives of multiple HQ levels, and as well as the fundamental roles of HQ relevant to contemporary corporations.

One of the key inflection points which seemed to provoke further organizational research on HQ goes back to Alfred Chandler's (1962) seminal work on corporate strategy and structure. This contribution by Chandler involved in-depth case studies of large firms in the USA such as DuPont, Sears, and

General Motors to discuss the emergence of the multidivisional organizational form (the 'M-Form').

Due to Chandler's pivotal research on these well-established corporations, it became clear that the M-Form arose as an organizational response to coping with substantial firm growth and expansion in multiple products lines, or geographic markets (Berg, 1969; Chandler, 1991). Moreover, managing this multidimensional complexity, along with separating the management of day-to-day responsibilities for tactical operations versus long term strategic planning, gave visibility to the HQ as a separate organizational unit to effectively focus on the latter (Williamson, 1975; Freeland, 1996).

According to Goold, Campbell & Alexander (1994), the executives, management and other associated human resources within firms that have roles beyond those in the operating units, or not directly running a business can be defined as the 'corporate parent'. This is the foundational definition of HQ that I have used in this study as it remains relevant whether a firm is multibusiness or multinational. Throughout the literature, other terms for corporate parent and HQ have been used including corporate center, corporate or global HQ, general office, central office, central administrative office, and parent company (Menz, Kunisch & Collis, 2015).

Most of the fundamental theoretical perspectives on HQ have been derived from two research streams on multibusiness and multinational firms. The multibusiness firm studies historically tended to have a strong focus on corporate strategy and organization design taking into consideration HQ's ability

to create economic value (Hungenberg, 1993; Goold, 1996a; Goold 1996b) for the overall firm by appropriately parenting the product, business, or industry orientated subunits (Menz, Kunisch & Collis, 2015).

Several of these studies were based on case study research on large multibusiness corporations and two notable exemplars are Goold & Campbell (2002a) and Galbraith (2014). In both contributions, there is clear perspective that HQ's main function is to create value at the parent level over and beyond the operating subunits.

Other researchers share this viewpoint, hence the development of concepts such as corporate advantage (Collis & Montgomery, 1998) and parenting advantage (Campbell, Goold & Alexander, 1995b). While competitive advantage (Porter, 1987) focuses on firms directly competing against and besting industry peers, these other concepts are predicated on the parent unearthing superior performance for the portfolio of businesses it owns, relative to how these same businesses would perform as stand-alone units, or under the ownership of another parent company (Goold, Campbell & Alexander, 1994).

The multinational literature takes on some different but related perspectives on HQ as an organizational phenomenon compared to the multibusiness stream. Conceptual and survey research in the 1960-1970's (e.g. Rutenberg, 1969; McInnes, 1971; Schollhammer, 1971) provided key insights into the roles, activities, and structures of multinational firms especially in USA and European markets. Additionally, seminal contributions published in the 1980's by the likes

of Baliga & Jaeger (1984) and Bartlett & Ghoshal (1989), highlighted and significantly promulgated further research on multinational firms, taking into consideration the challenges which HQs faced in dealing with their subsidiaries across several different geographic regions.

While studies on HQ in multibusiness firms tend to take on a ‘top-down’ parenting perspective as it relates to value-creation, research on multinational firms frequently take on a ‘bottom-up’ unit viewpoint on how the independent subsidiaries create aggregate firm value (Kostova, Marano & Tallman, 2016). Therefore, in the multinational research landscape, ideas from control theory (Child 1972; Child, 1973; Eisenhardt, 1985), social network theory (Granovetter, 1973; Hansen 1999), agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Fama, 1980) and resource-dependence theory (Scherer & Lee, 2002) have all been utilized to study HQ’s roles in managing the issues inherent to the web of operating units that typically exist in large multinational firms.

While I accept the strong intellectual roots of HQ stemming from research on multibusiness and multinational firms, their sheer designations may inadvertently suggest that the archetypical anatomy of contemporary corporations are also not inherently multi-level. Therefore, perhaps it is unsurprising that empirical investigations on HQs at multiple levels have not attracted a significant amount of attention in organizational research (Menz, Kunisch & Collis, 2015). Nonetheless, I must still give credit to those scholars who have recognized the existence and contributed to our knowledge of multiple HQ levels in large firm contexts.

Garvin & Levesque (2008) is an illustrative example of a study that deeply examined the nuance of multiple levels in complex corporate structures. Their research involved directly interviewing management at different levels in large corporations which participated in the retail, restaurant, and banking industries. The findings from this study suggest that these types of firms employ four or more levels of management with specific responsibilities to support the execution of the strategy set by the CHQ.

Additionally, there are several other researchers who strongly acknowledge the presence and rationale for multiple HQ levels in the contemporary corporation with divisional configurations and responsibilities (Heenan, 1979; Chandler 1991; Goold & Campell, 2002a; Birkinshaw et al., 2006; Alfoldi, Clegg & McGaughey, 2012). Many of these studies admit that the roles, activities, structures, and other characteristics associated with having HQ at multiple levels, is highly contingent on internal organizational and external environmental contexts.

There exists an abundance of research specifically on the role of HQ, and in summary, there appears to be consensus on two main roles. The first main role is in relation to carrying out obligatory, administrative and loss preventative activities (Foss, 1997), which are critical responsibilities especially in large publicly trading companies given the associated legal and regulatory governance requirements (Collis, Young & Goold, 2007). Some of the typical functions that will be found in firms mostly at the CHQ level, to discharge these functions are corporate reporting, legal tax, treasury, investor relations, audit, risk, and compliance (Couto & Neilson, 2007).

The second main role can be simply described as being entrepreneurial (Chandler, 1962; 1991) or value creation (Goold, Campbell & Alexander, 1994). In the published literature, several types of roles have been identified which are carried out with the intention to add value above and beyond the business units. Some key examples include business development and mergers and acquisitions (M&A) (Goold, Campbell & Alexander, 1994), strategic planning (Campbell, 1999; Kaplan & Norton, 2005), financial and investment acumen (Galbraith, 2014), leveraging economies of scale and scope (Teece, 1982; Goold & Campbell, 2002a), resource allocation and knowledge sharing (Goold & Campbell, 2002b; Campbell & Szulanski, 2016) and cross-unit collaboration (Martin & Eisenhardt, 2010).

Authors such as Chandler (1991) and Birkinshaw et al. (2006) acknowledge that both general roles are often carried out at multiple HQ levels, albeit represented in different forms depending on the firm's strategy, structure, and environmental context. However, even with all the well-established foundational contributions on HQ articulated above, more recent research accepts that we still have insufficient knowledge on what and how the roles of HQ are carried out at different organizational levels (Ciabuschi, Dellestrand & Holm, 2012; Menz, Kunisch & Collis, 2015). When adding the particularity of what roles multiple HQ levels play in integrative activities such as cross-unit collaboration, the knowledge gap widens, hence providing more opportunities to enhance our understanding of this organizational phenomenon.

Organizational Integration and Devices to Support Cross-Unit Collaboration

Like corporate parenting and the role of HQ addressed in the prior section, the existing body of literature on organizational integration is vast but however, there are still openings to elaborate and boost our learnings on how adequate integration is achieved (Castañer & Ketokivi, 2018). In this section, I start by defining organizational integration acknowledging seminal contributions, including referral to the internal and external organizational views on integration. I then focus on the literature on integrative devices, which I deem to be theoretically and managerially relevant for the positioning of this research on the role of multiple HQ levels in cross-unit collaboration. I also use this section to provide early indicators of opportunities for theoretical elaboration of integrative devices.

Organizational integration has been addressed in various academic management disciplines, including strategy (Glouberman & Mintzberg, 2001; Porter, 2001), production and operations management (Chandra & Kumar, 2001), innovation (Dosi, 1988), and information technology and systems (Truman, 2000). However, one of the most influential contributions associated with organizational integration is Lawrence & Lorsch's (1967). In this study, they defined integration as a process by which unity is achieved among subunits to accomplish some organizational goal or specific task.

More recently, other authors such as Barki & Pinsonneault (2005), have expanded the definition of integration taking into consideration firm externalities. Thus, they define organizational integration as the extent to which interdependent units make up a unified whole, not only in relation to activities

occurring within a firm, but also between firms which may incorporate producers, suppliers, customers, and other partners in the respective value chains. The differentiation between the internal versus external aspects of integration have been thoroughly investigated in the strategy literature (Porter, 1985) as well as in transaction cost economics (Williamson, 1985).

I recognize from previous studies that our understanding and definitions of organizational integration has continually evolved due to a multitude of contributions in diverse academic areas (Barki & Pinsonneault, 2005). My research on organizational integration, in the form of cross-unit collaboration, is in respect to the role that multiple HQ levels play in that regard, which is characteristically internal from a structural perspective, and therefore my view is that that Lawrence & Lorsch's (1967) definition is still applicable and relevant in this case.

In this study, I define a unit (or subunit) to represent a business unit, line of business, subsidiary, operating company, function, or department depending on the contextual circumstances associated with the integration challenge being addressed. The reason for this supple definition is because the reality of the modern large firm is simultaneously multi-level, multinational and multibusiness and, therefore, integration internally can occur along the many dimensions and across these various types of organizational units. In addition to this, I leveraged perspectives from Martin & Eisenhardt (2010) to define cross-unit collaboration as integrative activity exhibited between multiple units within a large corporation based on the intention to create economic value. Also, the

notion of cross-unit collaboration may take various forms and have different objectives depending on the nature of the activities and units involved.

My second research question seeks to understand how various HQ levels behave and operate to support organizationally integrative activities which involve cross-unit collaboration. Given this inquiry, I relied on the concept of integrative devices—defined by Lawrence & Lorsch (1967) as a set of tools in which management of a firm deploys to achieve integration—to carry out my research. Further to this, it was important to leverage recent work by Castañer & Ketokivi's (2018), who developed a typology of integrative devices incorporating perspectives from contingency theory, and other organizational research streams.

They identified seven integrative devices: authority, collective incentives, communication, cross-unit structure, formalization, multi-skilling, and socialization. These devices collectively address different forms of integration including those that are behavioral, cultural, and cognitive in nature (Ghoshal & Gratton, 2002). Table 2.1 provides definitions of these integrative devices and includes some key references associated with their theoretical backgrounds.

Table 2.1: Summary of Castañer & Ketokivi's Typology of Integrative Devices

Integrative Device	Definition & Theoretical Context
Authority	The use of greater decision-making and overall organizational power by virtue of position to achieve integration often by the referral to a superior (Miller, 1992; Leavitt, 2005).
Collective Incentives	Implementing collective incentives to management and broader organizational stakeholders to foster integration (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Gupta & Govindarajan, 1986; Ghoshal & Gratton, 2002).

Integrative Device	Definition & Theoretical Context
Communication	Deploying the appropriate forms of communication, inclusion, and participation to ensure a desired integrative outcome is met (Ketokivi & Castañer, 2004).
Cross-Unit Structure	This is a structural device, that may be permanent (e.g. matrix organizational structure) or temporary (e.g. cross-functional team), put in place to help achieve some form of integration (Lawrence & Lorsch, 1967; Adler, 1995; Galbraith, 2014).
Formalization	Standard operating procedures, plans and formal routines governing organizational subunits to support integration (Nelson & Winter, 1982).
Multi-skilling	Leveraging human resources with experience to promote collaboration and other forms of integration. These resources would have attained a generalist capability by moving through the organization via job rotation or other modalities (Hackman & Oldham, 1975; Edström & Galbraith, 1977).
Socialization	The use of cultural alignment and identification, relationships between organizational actors and social events to facilitate stronger bonds to increase the likelihood of achieving integration (Granovetter, 1973; Ouchi, 1980; Albert, Ashforth & Dutton, 2000).

Source: Castañer & Ketokivi (2018); Author's Synthesis

Each of the seven integrative devices are grounded in theory. However, as scholars continually seek a more complete theory of organizational integration, further research incorporating greater insight into specific integration challenges within various organizational environments is still to be adequately championed (Castañer & Ketokivi, 2018). To this end, my study aims to elaborate the application of integrative devices, contextualized within an organizational environment specifically examining how multiple HQ levels deploy these devices to support the cross-unit collaboration efforts.

Synthesis

After reviewing literature from on the foundational areas of corporate parenting and organizational integration, there are two main key takeaways that are important to highlight in relation to my research topic. The first takeaway is that several authors have indicated that modern large corporations are simultaneously both multibusiness and multinational (Prahalad & Doz, 1987; Goold, Campbell & Alexander, 1994). Therefore, continually integrating perspectives on these historically separate research streams remains hugely important (Menz, Kunisch & Collis, 2015), while simultaneously contributing further insights on the multiple levels of HQ that typically exist within the modern corporation.

Secondly, taking cues from seminal research by Lawrence & Lorsch (1967), one of the main challenges for HQ at any level is finding the right balance between integration and differentiation. Moreover, when integration is sought, we know that there are various integrative devices that can be deployed to help capture this desire, but enhancing our empirical understanding of how this occurs, particularly in large firm contexts with multiple HQ levels, can be scholastically and practically insightful helpful (Martin & Eisenhardt, 2010; Menz et al., 2015).

In the next chapter, I describe the research methodology behind how this study was conducted, setting the path for the articulation of my contribution that will help to elaborate on some of the theoretical concepts highlighted, as well as narrow some of the gaps discussed in this review of the literature.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter describes my research methodology, and it commences by first providing insights on the research design, including the rationale for utilizing a multiple case study design for theory elaboration (Ketokivi & Choi, 2014). The chapter continues with presenting details on the research setting followed by a section with reflections on being an insider researcher. I then present the logic behind the how the cases were selected, along with details on the profiles of each case. After that, I describe the approach to key informant selection, data collection, data management and analysis. The last sections address issues of trustworthiness and ethical considerations, and then I close with a chapter summary.

Research design

In this study, my goal is to enrich knowledge on the role of multiple HQ levels in cross-unit collaboration and it involves the examination of various contexts to attain multiple perspectives of the similar phenomena from different organizational actors. A qualitative approach to constructing knowledge from eliciting perspectives and interpreting experiences from different informants was considered suitable for a study of this nature. More specifically, it was deemed appropriate to use a multiple case study to conduct a thorough investigation in a real-life firm context (Yin, 2014), thereby strengthening our comprehension in the organizational area under examination.

Five organizational initiatives at Massy were selected as cases. Massy is a diversified corporation operating in different territories with multiple HQ levels that participate in the development and execution of initiatives which feature cross-unit collaboration. Further details on the case study organization are provided below.

The research design used in my study leverages many of the key characteristics associated with theory generation approaches such as Eisenhardt's (1989) inductive theory building case study method. However, for the aims of my research are better described as a theory elaboration instead of theory building (Ketokivi & Choi, 2014). Specifically, my objective is to apply *existing* concepts on parenting (Goold, Campbell & Alexander, 1994; Goold & Campbell, 2002b) and organizational integration (Castañer & Ketokivi, 2018) in a specific empirical context, to examine their contextual empirical manifestations. Such examinations can help us understand important nuances and, consequently, lead to an elaboration of the concepts.

Using these existing ideas to support my research agenda inside a large corporation with multinational, multibusiness and multi-level organizational characteristics, presented a diversity of rich contexts to support building on established theoretical foundations. Given these diverse factors, it made sense to select multiple cases for the purposes of identifying similarities and contrasting results. Employing multiple cases also enabled a replication process (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007) and provided the opportunity to yield analytical generalization (Yin, 2014).

There were six main steps in the overall research design (see also Figure 3.1):

1. Reviewing the literature on relevant organizational theories as well as assessing the appropriate research methods to ultimately support a determination of the case study modality.
2. Selecting suitable Massy initiatives to be examined as cases.
3. Selecting the key informants (55 total) to provide original data on the cases.
4. Conducting semi-structured interviews (Yin, 2014) with the informants all conducted face-to-face. The interviews were complemented by secondary data sources such as public filings (e.g. annual reports), internal company documents (e.g. strategic plans) and news articles were also utilized when applicable.
5. Coding the contemporaneously created field notes (Bloomberg & Volpe, 2016); checking inter-rater reliability.
6. Conducting both within-case and cross-cases analyses of the five cases (Eisenhardt, 1989).

Figure 3.1: Research Design Synopsis & Process

Source: Author's analysis

Case study organizational context

The empirical material for this dissertation comes from Massy (previously Neal & Massy), a diversified corporation operating primarily in the Caribbean and Latin America. The company was founded by Harry Neal and Charles Massy in Trinidad & Tobago in the 1920's as an engineering services company (Neal & Massy, 2010). In the 1950's, the company became an established player in the industrial equipment industry with tractors, cranes and compressors for sale or lease, complemented with integrated service offerings (Neal & Massy, 2010).

By the 1960s, the company realized that growth would be constrained by the inherent limited market size that a small island state can offer, and therefore

strategic decisions were made to diversify into new industry segments, as well as to grow in new territories within the region (Neal & Massy, 2010). From the 1970's onwards to the 2000's, regional growth continued to be a strategic priority, and most of the firm's new business diversification and geographic expansion activities were derived from M&A activity (Neal & Massy, 2010). In 2008, Neal & Massy acquired the Barbados Shipping & Trading Co. Ltd., resulting in the company becoming one of the largest companies in the Caribbean region (Neal & Massy, 2008). Also in 2011, the company commenced assessing viable options for market entry into Latin America, and eventually expanded into Colombia through acquisitions in the automotive and energy sectors (Neal & Massy, 2011; Massy, 2014).

In 2014, Neal & Massy rebranded to Massy with all the key operating entities operating under one corporate banner (Massy, 2014). Today, Massy is publicly listed on the Trinidad & Tobago Stock Exchange and Jamaica Stock Exchange as an investment holding company with just under US\$2 billion in annual revenue generated from operations in more than 8 territories in the Caribbean, Latin America, and Florida (USA) with over 13,000 employees (Massy, 2022). The company's corporate headquarter operations are based in Trinidad & Tobago and Barbados with its fiscal year ending in September.

The main industries in which Massy participates are food retail, distribution, automotive and industrial equipment dealerships, gas products and energy services, technology services, general insurance, money transfer services, consumer finance, and real estate. At the time that this study was conducted,

the company was structured along six main business segments (see Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Massy's Portfolio Structure as at the end of FY 2019

Source: Compiled from internal company documents

Each segment represents a combination of sub-sectors with an Executive Vice President (EVP) or Senior Vice President (SVP) responsible for strategic and financial oversight directly reporting to the President & Group CEO. Within each business segment, there exists operating companies which are run by CEOs, Managing Directors or General Managers who directly report to an EVP or SVP. The firm has three main vertical organizational levels namely Group/Corporate, Portfolio/Business Unit/Line of Business and Operating Company and hence, it has three concomitant HQ levels which are the CHQ, DHQ and OHQ, respectively.

Given the information provided thus far on Massy, it would be natural for many to describe the firm as a conglomerate or business group (Kock & Guillen,

2001), which are diversified organizational forms commonly present in developing economies (Guillen, 2000; Ramachandran et al., 2013). However, while certain definitions are useful for classifying firms based on their level of industry diversification, I would like to acknowledge the fact that firms such as Massy have several different characteristics suggesting that they can be described as simultaneously being multibusiness, multinational and multi-level. The focus of my research is not about firm stratification, but I believe it is important to recognize the multidimensionality of Massy because this inherent constitution provided an interesting research environment to conduct my study, taking into consideration the realities and complexities associated with a contemporary large-scale corporation.

Massy is organized around six business segments and an apt way to describe how the firm is managed would be to borrow Alfred Sloan's terminology of 'decentralization with coordinated control' (Garvin & Levesque, 2006). Given the differences in the composition of each segment, decentralization was deemed appropriate to enable focus on industry priorities and idiosyncrasies. At the same time, coordination to attain alignment across the company in some key areas (e.g. financial and legal policies, core values) was still required and governed by the Board of Directors, President & Group CEO, and the Corporate Office.

As I sought to further expand our understanding of the role that multiple HQ levels play in cross-unit collaboration, choosing an environment that hosts a multiplicity of integration challenges involving various organizational levels was

required. Based on all that I have intimated thus far, I submit that Massy provides a suitable empirical case setting.

Self-reflections as an insider

I am not merely the researcher in this study, I am also a long-time corporate insider. I have included this section not only to make transparent the fact that I was an insider, but also to provide key insights on how my being an insider is relevant.

I am currently Senior Vice President of Corporate Strategy & Transactions at Massy, where I have been employed for 19 years. During my tenure, I have held various roles spanning all three HQ levels in business operations, strategic planning and analysis, and corporate development with direct exposure to most of the industry segments within Massy. These include retail, distribution, manufacturing, shipping and logistics, energy, automotive, information technology and communications, consumer finance, and real estate.

I joined Massy in 2003 as a Management Trainee in Barbados and worked my way up through several positions to my current role. While my primary role and responsibilities lie at the CHQ level, I have several additional executive responsibilities including Chairman of the real estate business line, overseeing a holding company in Barbados, and Director on several of Massy's subsidiary boards.

From my knowledge and experience working for a large firm in the Caribbean and Latin America, empirical research leveraging insights from such corporations within the region did not seem as forthcoming. Admittedly, when I

first started the doctoral program at IE Business School, my mind was set on carrying out further research on the relationship between unrelated diversification and performance using datasets from publicly trading firms domiciled in the Caribbean.

While studies of this kind have yielded important findings in other geographic market spaces (Berger & Ofek, 1995; Khanna & Palepu, 1997; Villalonga, 2004; Chakrabarti et al., 2007), I eventually decided to pivot, and chose a case study approach to seek insights on *how* things occurred within the context of a large corporation to which I had privileged access. This decision did not come so easily as it evolved after several discussions and debates with my advisor, but the journey of conducting research oftentimes leads to a meandering path.

From my experience working with Massy at multiple organizational levels, across various territories and businesses, I witnessed firsthand several challenges and opportunities associated with organizational integration. Further to this and after reviewing an article by Martin & Eisenhardt (2010), I became more intrigued by better understanding what firms specifically do to achieve cross-unit collaboration and particularly, how they go about doing it. This curiosity led me to reflect and identify specific projects or initiatives in Massy that involved a significant amount of cross-unit collaboration in various forms.

Many of the roles I had in Massy furnished me with lots of exposure and a deep understanding of the company's strategic plans and priorities. As a longstanding employee, I have built many strong personal and professional relationships, and I always had a good sense of 'what was going on' within

Massy. Therefore, it was not difficult for me to develop a list of initiatives which involved cross-unit collaboration and integration in general. Additionally, I knew most of the senior executives and managers directly involved in these initiatives and therefore attaining access to them or others involved who I did not have a direct relationship with did not present a challenge.

In summary, I consider my being an insider a relevant characteristic of my research design and methodology (Morey & Luthans, 1984). I have special knowledge, relationships and privileged access which enabled me to strategically maneuver within the firm in a manner which helped me to ultimately achieve the research objectives. Personally knowing almost all my informants also enabled a special rapport with those who served as the most important source of my data. The initiatives I have examined in my research are strategic and confidential, and I had to seek a way to collect data on them, and write about them, in a way that did not breach confidentiality.

Case selection logic

In this study, a unit is defined in relation to the specific context, and may refer to a portfolio, business unit, line of business, operating company or even a functional department. Similarly, cross-unit collaboration may take different forms and it may have different objectives, depending on the associated integration challenge. From 2015, I commenced the process of reviewing various internal documents, particularly corporate and business unit level strategic plans, to identify initiatives which involved various forms of cross-unit collaboration.

After the first scan of the company's plans, I initially identified eight, primarily *cross-business* initiatives. After further reviewing literature on the role of HQ in large firms, I decided to seek out a more diverse set of initiatives which encompassed collaboration across both businesses and geographies. This was done as multiple perspectives of the phenomenon being examined were desired, particularly given the reality of how cross-unit collaboration occurs within firms such as Massy that are large multinationals with a broad industry scope.

After further iterations of assessing internal documents, I then settled on a list of four initiatives, which were all both cross-business and cross-country. However, in November 2017, after receiving feedback from my Proposal Defense Committee, I revisited the case selection criteria to include HQ level of origination, as the vertical dimension of the organization with respect to cross-unit collaboration was not sufficiently considered.

Eventually, taking the feedback into consideration, I finalized the selection of five initiatives with varying organizational contexts, all of which had characteristics of cross-unit collaboration that transpired across multiple HQ levels, businesses, and geographic territories. I settled on five cases based on the sampling logic that served to focus my efforts on theoretically useful situations (Eisenhardt, 1989). Additionally, including more cases would have been impractical given the length of time it would have taken to collect data from interviewing several more informants, and complete the research within a feasible period.

Profile of the cases

The five initiatives selected as cases within the research setting are Guyana Retail Entry, Own Brands, Corporate Rebranding, Regional Procurement, and Group Policies. I briefly introduce each initiative in the following and describe the logic by which I used the key informants in each case.

Guyana Retail Entry

This case involves the project organization to support the expansion of an existing business into a new geographic territory. In December 2013, Massy's parent board granted approval for the Integrated Retail Business Unit to proceed with new retail site development for Massy Stores to enter the Guyana market. Massy has a long-standing history of operating several businesses (e.g. wholesale distribution, automotive and industrial equipment dealerships, gas products and money transfer services) in Guyana (Massy, 2015), and part of its corporate strategy was to pursue further growth of existing businesses in this territory. At the time, Massy Stores had operations in four other countries namely Trinidad & Tobago, Barbados, St. Lucia, and St. Vincent & the Grenadines, and Guyana was identified as a priority market for expansion.

To put more structure around the implementation of this initiative, the SVP & Executive Chairman responsible for Massy Stores regionally formed a Steering Committee that had strategic oversight and governance of the project. The SVP appointed one of the existing retail operating company CEOs from St. Lucia as the Project Owner who was responsible for leading the Project Team charged with planning and execution.

The main integration challenge involved the Project Team working with different resources from existing retail operations in other territories as well as other resources on the ground in Guyana, all in the effort to collaborate on opening the new store. Figure 3.3 shows the organizational structure and reporting relationships between the HQ units involved in the Guyana Retail Entry case. Informants for this case were selected based on their direct participation on the Project Team and included people from the DHQ and OHQ levels only.

Figure 3.3: Organizational Structure and Relationships between the key HQ Levels involved in the Guyana Retail Entry Case

Source: Developed from author's knowledge and internal company documents

Own Brands

This initiative originated at the DHQ level of the Integrated Retail Business Unit, which encapsulates the company's retail (Massy Stores) and distribution (Massy Distribution) businesses as illustrated in Figure 3.3 above. As internally defined by Massy, Own Brands are consumer packed goods that are marketed under brands which are legally owned by Massy Stores or Massy Distribution for sale in various channels and markets. In financial year 2018, the Own Brands portfolio (see Figure 3.4 below) in aggregate generated revenue of ~US\$33.5 million and were segmented as follows:

1. Retail Private Brands: Brands owned by Massy Stores operating companies which are sold exclusively in Massy Stores (e.g. Cuisine, Hi-Dee, People's Choice).
2. Exclusive Brands: Brands not owned by the Massy Group but sold exclusively in Massy Stores in specific territories (e.g. Waitrose).
3. Distribution Own Brands: Brands owned by Massy Distribution operating companies which are sold to both Massy Stores and the wider market (e.g. Valrico, Pharmatex).

Figure 3.4: Massy Integrated Retail's Own Brands Portfolio - July 2019

Source: Internal company documents

Historically, most of the brands were managed independently within the respective operating companies. The objective of the initiative was to transition the management of Own Brands to a more regionalized oversight structure to coordinate activities and capture economies of scale and scope, with the operating companies evolving to focus more on local execution. Some of the activities that were being considered for regionalization are marketing, labelling, direct procurement, and selection of contract manufacturers. The expectation was that these activities would result in enhanced operating margins from reduced cost of goods sold and operating expenditure. Also, a more regionalized strategic approach to marketing was expected to result in stronger sales growth.

The main integration challenge was to strengthen collaboration across businesses within the Integrated Retail Business Unit to gain consensus and align on a new approach to managing the portfolio of Own Brands. Key informants from the DHQ and OHQ within the Integrated Retail Business Unit were selected based on their participation in the project.

Corporate Rebranding

This case concerns a group-wide initiative associated with the planning, preparation, and implementation of rebranding the legacy company banners (see Figure 3.5) to the new corporate identity: Massy. The idea for corporate rebranding was conceived at the CHQ level, and the main strategic rationale was to introduce a mechanism to create a more collaborative enterprise that enabled greater synergies, and alignment around a common identity, purpose, and core values (Massy, 2014). It should be noted that the corporate brand architecture of Massy is included below in Figure 3.6.

The integration challenge in Corporate Rebranding was how the firm would reorganize to gain internal consensus to roll out the company-wide organizational initiative. The company invested approximately US\$9 million in the financial year 2014 to implement the corporate rebranding initiative (Massy, 2014) with direct involvement from employees at all organizational levels across all territories. As such, the sample of informants selected were key persons directly involved in the conceptualization and implementation hailing from different HQ levels.

Figure 3.5: Sample of Legacy Banners before Corporate Rebranding

Source: Internal company documents

Figure 3.6: Massy's Corporate Brand Architecture

Source: Compiled from internal company documents

Regional Procurement

The economic challenges experienced in 2016 and 2017 in key territories negatively affected the company's performance, which forced Massy to put more focus cost optimization (Massy, 2017). Therefore, Massy engaged the global management consulting firm, McKinsey & Company, to help the organization through an initiative to centralize activities related to the procurement of indirect goods and services (Massy, 2017). Indirect spend categories are the goods and services purchased by the businesses that are not available for resale, and the main rationale was to achieve greater

efficiencies and reduce expenditure through the deployment of global best practices in procurement (Massy, 2017).

Classic examples of these categories are office supplies, telecommunications, occupancy costs, business travel, freight and logistics, professional services, marketing and advertising, facilities, maintenance and repairs, utilities, and contract labor. To provide an illustration of the integration challenge being addressed, Figure 3.7 shows a snapshot of the fragmented array of various logistics service providers for ocean freight utilized by Massy operating companies.

Figure 3.7: Universe of Massy's Logistics Service Providers in 2018

Source: Internal company documents

Regional Procurement originated at, and was led by, the CHQ. The main integration challenge was to align the various divisions and operating entities on a centralized approach to procuring these indirect goods and services. For

example, in the business travel segment, there was an initiative to align the preferred hotels used in key markets based on the rates and other terms negotiated. Several key executives, managers, and associates from all three HQ levels were involved in this enterprise-wide initiative, and hence informants were appropriately selected based on their participation in the project.

Group Policies

The Group Policies initiative Massy involves policy measures that provide standardization across the entire firm. Examples of such policies would be The Code of Conduct Ethics Policy and the Conflict of Interest Policy with the Group Legal department at the CHQ level taking the lead on implementation. The integration challenge is based on the efforts required by various internal stakeholders at different organizational levels to implement these policies across businesses which operate in different industries and territories.

Therefore, I selected key informants at all three HQ levels in functional departments that were involved in such activities to align policies in their respective areas. The departments targeted were Human Resources, IT, Legal, Health, Safety, Security & Environment (HSSE), and Risk Management. This initiative is perpetual in that policies are continuously reviewed at the company, and hence the integration challenge of continuously ensuring policy alignment remains.

Key informant selection

I selected informants non-randomly to be interviewed, and I commenced this process by holding informal preliminary discussions with a few key executives

who were likely to have relevant insight into the initiatives. Being an insider with a long tenure at Massy and having strong relationships with several internal stakeholders was critical in supporting key informant selection. I purposely targeted interviewees that would be able to provide rich insights enabling me to ultimately answer the research questions. After starting the interviewing process, discussions with various informants led me to other candidates to be added, which resulted in what is best described as 'snowball sampling' (Trochim & Donnelly, 2008).

The final list of 55 informants includes the President & Group CEO, 4 Executive Vice Presidents, 6 Senior Vice-Presidents, 11 Group Corporate Executives, 9 CEOs/Managing Directors/General Managers, 8 Divisional Corporate Executives, 6 Operating Company Directors, 7 Managers/Supervisors and 3 Associates. These informants collectively represented all three HQ levels – 15 from the CHQ (Group/Corporate), 19 from the DHQ (Portfolio/Business Unit/Line of Business) and 21 from the OHQ (Operating Company). All interviews were conducted in person in two of the main territories which are Trinidad & Tobago and Barbados, collectively representing over 70% of Massy's revenue in financial year 2019 (Massy, 2019; Massy, 2020). To maintain anonymity, I will not use the proper names of the informants but, instead, refer to them only by their respective positions within Massy.

A cross section of the informants were from various industry segments including retail, distribution, automotive dealerships, general insurance, consumer finance, technology services, manufacturing, and real estate. Also, several functional areas were adequately represented such as Finance, Legal, Human

Resources (HR), Information Technology (IT), Procurement, Marketing, Business Development, Corporate Communications and HSSE. The heterogeneity of the informants was intentional given that I sought persons who had direct involvement in the respective initiatives, as well as people who were positioned at different HQ levels in alignment with the theoretical sampling of the cases.

Moreover, I decided to interview each person only once and face-to-face, so I continually searched for informants until I reached a saturation point based on these collective criteria and in terms of practicality taking into consideration time and resource constraints. Table 3.1 shows the demography of key informants interviewed by case segmented by position and HQ level.

Table 3.1: Demographics of Key Informants

	Group Policies_CHQ	Corporate Rebranding_CHQ	Regional Procurement_CHQ	Own Brands_DHQ	Guyana Retail Entry_DHQ	All Cases
Total # of Informants = 55	15	15	14	7	4	55
President & Group CEO	0	1	0	0	0	1
Executive Vice President	0	2	2	0	0	4
Senior Vice President	1	2	1	1	1	6
Group Corporate Executive	5	2	4	0	0	11
CEO/MD/GM	0	2	5	2	0	9
Divisional Corporate Executive	3	2	1	1	1	8
Director	1	2	0	1	2	6
Manager/Supervisor	4	2	0	1	0	7
Associate	1	0	1	1	0	3
Other	0	0	0	0	0	0
Corporate: CHQ	6	4	5	0	0	15
Divisional: DHQ	5	5	4	3	2	19
Operating Company: OHQ	4	6	5	4	2	21

Source: Author's Analysis

Data collection and management

Data were collected from multiple sources and categorized as primary (interviews) and secondary (internal company documentation). As to the

primary data, the semi-structured approach provided me with the natural flexibility (Bryman, 2004) in the discussions allowing me to probe deeper on the specific inquiries when necessary, and it also allowed the interviewees to elaborate freely to get their points of view across in the responses. The combination of eliciting insights from several different informants via semi-structured interviews across multiple cases provided an enabling environment for abductive reasoning (Niiniluoto, 1999) to support the overall theory elaboration approach (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007). Other researchers such as Ketokivi (2006) for example, have made use of abduction to support the elaboration of contingency theory leveraging a case study on manufacturing flexibility strategies.

To develop the semi-structured approach, I first developed an overall interview protocol based on the research questions being addressed in the study. I conducted two pilot interviews in person on December 10th, 2018, to test out the protocol and receive any feedback from the pilot informants. These two sessions helped me to reshape my approach to future interviews taking on a more open and interactive disposition, rather than rigid interrogation of the informants, which ultimately led to more fruitful discussions.

The semi-structured interview guide focused on four questions:

1. What are the various roles of HQ in the Group?
2. What role does HQ play in supporting cross-unit collaboration?
3. What roles do/did the various levels of HQ (i.e. CHQ, DHQ, OHQ) play in this specific strategic initiative?

4. What mechanisms / integrative devices are/were put in place to ensure that cross-unit collaboration successfully occurs in this specific initiative?

After receiving approval from my advisor to proceed, I commenced the interview process in December 2018 by sending emails to the prospective informants formally inviting them and seeking approval for me to interview them for the purpose of my doctoral research. While participation in the study was voluntary, all the informants I approached accepted my invitation. I believe that being an insider and having strong relationships with several of the informants significantly assisted my efforts in attaining a 100% response rate.

Furthermore, this response rate also confirms that Massy executives and managers consider organizational integration critical for Massy. Once the confirmation response was sent, I then followed up with further emails or telephone calls to solidify a time, date, and location for the interview to take place (see Appendix B for an example of a redacted snapshot of an invitation and confirmation email exchange with one of the informants).

I was adamant about carrying out all interviews in person as I believed this would provide richer, more intimate discussions and it also created the opportunity to further elaborate on various topics given that I was literally 'sitting in the same room'. Being flexible in semi-structured interviews can oftentimes lead to tangential conversations that can be beneficial for drawing out additional relevant insights (Bryman, 2004). Consequently, all 55 interviews were conducted face-to-face in various locations in Trinidad & Tobago and Barbados between December 2018 and June 2019.

At the beginning of each interview, I recorded the informant's name, title, organizational level, case, date and start time on a clean sheet Microsoft Word template. I then provided the interviewee with additional context on the purpose of my research, the specific case study and interview guide with the four questions. I also reassured them that all data collected from the interview via responses will be treated as private and confidential, and that I would be required to specifically seek approval from them if there was a desire to disclose their identities or any sensitive information pertaining to the interview in future publications.

I considered recording the interviews potentially excessively intrusive.

Therefore, I chose to take contemporaneous notes in Microsoft Word based on informants' responses to protocol questions and the ensuing discussions. I continually sought clarifications throughout the interview and iteratively updated my notes as the conversations evolved. At the end of the interviews, I verbally read out what I had written in my notes and made adjustments based on the immediate feedback I received from the interviewee. Once the informant and I agreed that my notes were accurate, I terminated the interview.

In total, I conducted 54 of the 55 interviews in this manner which resulted in approximately 96 pages of transcribed field notes from 81 hours of interview time over a six-month period (see Appendix B). The last interview was done with the President & Group CEO, and it was recorded on my mobile phone. The insights from this interview were utilized as additional organizational background context and it should be noted that there was no coding done in this regard. I kept track of the progress I was making with the interviews over the

six months via Microsoft Excel. I developed a key informants repository tracker which recorded the status of each interview by categories—pending, invited, scheduled, in-progress and completed.

Secondary data was collected from publicly available information such as annual reports, investor presentations and news articles. I also utilized internal documents such as strategic plans, annual budget reviews, emails, memos, and consultant reports as data sources depending on the case. The process of collecting data from multiple sources is a common practice in case studies (Yin, 2014; Bloomberg & Volpe, 2016). By collecting data from different informants and different types of data sources supported triangulation (Jick, 1979; Homburg et al., 2012) thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of the overall research findings.

All data files associated with this research were organized, managed, and stored in Dropbox cloud storage in which my doctoral advisor was given full access. These files included the literature review material, all primary and secondary data sources, working documents, analytical models, dissertation manuscripts, final defense presentations and any other files that were relevant to my research. The contemporaneous interview notes were captured and coded in Microsoft Word, and the analysis was executed using a combination of Microsoft Excel and Microsoft PowerPoint. The next section will provide greater details on the coding process applied.

Data coding

In this section, I will outline my approach to coding the contemporaneous field notes which was the output from the semi-structured interviews. Considering that I inscribed the field notes simultaneously during the interviews, and I also attained informant confirmation of veracity before the end of each session, there was no need to rewrite the field notes. However, I still performed an initial review of all the field notes in detail, after all the interviews were completed, enabling a level of immersion that helped me to get more familiar with the insights provided to support coding and analysis.

My case study research methodology was designed to support the elaboration of theory, so it was important to identify and harness key existing theoretical concepts to assist with addressing my research objectives. The theoretical positioning of my research lies at the intersection of corporate parenting with respect to the role of HQ and organizational integration vis-à-vis cross-unit collaboration. Therefore, I leveraged the theoretical constructs from these two literature streams which formed the categorization schemes required to execute coding of the interview inscriptions. This technique does share some similarities with traditional content analysis (Bloomberg & Volpe, 2016) given that I began the process with a predetermined categorization scheme. However, the salient feature to note here is that coding in this study is about linking data to preexisting concepts to see how they can be theoretically elaborated (Ketokivi & Choi, 2014) as they are further enriched with empirical content derived from the various contexts under investigation.

Firstly, on corporate parenting and the role of HQ, I applied Goold & Campbell's (2002b) five parenting propositions of Select, Build, Stretch, Link and Leverage to code the notated responses associated with the first two questions in the interview guide. More specifically, I used my judgement to assign parenting propositions, based on their definitions, to as many applicable response statements in the field notes. The way the coding was done in practice is that I used the 'Comment' feature in Microsoft Word to assign codes to each statement, literally writing the name of the proposition. Figure 3.8 provides an example of the coded field notes on responses to Interview Questions 1 and 2.

As Figure 3.8 shows, the fourth code from the top includes the additional comments which were borne out of the inter-rater reliability process (Bloomberg & Volpe, 2016) put in place. After I completed the first round of coding on the field notes, I notified my advisor to review and provide his feedback in an updated file. If he did not include additional comments on the code, then there was agreement, otherwise he would place a note such as the one below in Figure 3.8 indicating "This looks like Leverage to me as well". My advisor's feedback articulated his view that the Leverage parenting proposition seemed to be applicable in this case along with the Link proposition.

We would then meet to discuss the feedback and based on that discussion, and assign "Partial" or "Disagree" to the code along with a final position on the proposition. In this specific case, we partially agreed that the Link proposition was the primary parenting proposition in place. Even when there was disagreement, we ensured that there was always sufficient intellectual debate taking into consideration both theoretical perspectives as well as my privileged

understanding of the internal context. Overall, this interactive process with the advisor served as an inter-rater reliability check in my coding procedure.

Figure 3.8: Sample of Coded Field Notes - Responses to Interview Questions

1-2

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the various roles of HQ in the Group? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ “When I think of HQ, I think CHQ”. ○ From that perspective, the role of CHQ is to provide guidance to the companies – one of the main roles is advisory in relation to Finance, Legal, HR, Strategy, “IT not so much”. ○ Most departments in Massy Ltd provide advisory services to the companies. ○ “They are kinda like a watchdog too”. They look after the company on behalf of the shareholders “guiding the Group as a whole”. ○ The CHQ keeps the businesses in line with what the shareholders want. ○ Providing shared services to the businesses (e.g. Corporate Reporting, Legal). ○ The CHQ is primarily functional in nature, but it “can also operate like an operating company” (e.g. it is delivering advisory services similar to consulting and accounting firms, and therefore they behave similarly in this regard). • What role does HQ play in supporting cross-unit collaboration? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ “I don’t think that the CHQ plays a role in cross-unit collaboration”, but more so the DHQ (e.g. Massy Distribution in Trinidad sent people from their operations to Guyana to help Massy Distribution (Guyana) set up their new warehouse – sharing of best practices is a strategic priority for the Distribution Line of Business). ○ For any cross-unit collaboration between the businesses, the DHQ is the level that initiates and takes responsibility “for making it happen”. ○ The DHQ executives talk to each other and organically collaborate on areas of opportunity between their businesses. Lots of these collaborations occur informally at various meetings (e.g. Executive Committee and Investment Committee Meetings). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jeremy Nurse Link Proposition <p>Original code assigned by author</p> <p>Final position after inter-rater reliability process</p> <p>Feedback from advisor if not aligned</p>
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Source: Author’s Field Notes

Secondly, on organizational integration with respect to cross-unit collaboration, I applied Castañer & Ketokivi’s (2018) typology of seven integrative devices— authority, collective incentives, communication, cross-unit structure, formalization, multi-skilling, and socialization—to code the inscribed responses from the latter two interview questions. I followed a similar process to coding parenting propositions articulated above where I used my judgement in this

case to assign the codes of the integrative devices to the contemporaneous field notes using Microsoft Word in the same manner. However, the process used for reviewing the codes in collaboration with my advisor was approached differently.

The latter two questions were designed to elicit responses specific to the case the informant participated in. As an insider, I had a significantly greater understanding of the idiosyncrasies associated with each case relative to my advisor. Therefore, we decided that it was better to conduct an iterative peer debriefing (Bloomberg & Volpe, 2016) on the integrative device codes compared to the inter-rater reliability process we undertook with the parenting propositions. Figure 3.9 provides an example of the coded field notes on responses to Interview Questions 3 and 4.

In Figure 3.9, two key features of the coding output merit attention. Firstly, peer debriefing often resulted in an update to my initial thinking on the integrative devices coded. For example, in the fourth and sixth codes from the top based on the responses to Interview Question 4, cross-unit structure was supplanted by communication and socialization, respectively. While peer debriefing was the main reason for these adjustments, the continual reflection and enfolding of the literature (Eisenhardt, 1989) on the existing theories also influenced my thoughts on iterating accordingly.

Figure 3.9: Sample of Coded Field Notes-Responses to Interview Questions 3-4

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What roles do/did the various levels of HQ (i.e. CHQ, DHQ, OHQ) play in this specific strategic initiative? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CHQ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The Group CEO reviewed the strategy and “stretched it” given that the CHQ has a “larger perspective”. ▪ The CHQ ratified the Own Brands initiative developed by the DHQ and “gave it power and scope and space to pursue this strategy”. ○ DHQ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Developed the Own Brands strategy and took it to the CHQ for feedback. ▪ The DHQ is working on answering the question: “how do we execute this strategy?” ▪ Resource allocation – appointing a Regional Commercial Director, earmarking key resources within the operating companies, hiring external consultants, financial resources. ▪ Reviewing and designing the appropriate organizational structures to further develop and implement the initiative. ○ OHQ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The role of the OHQ is to allocate the necessary resources at the operating level. ▪ Adopt the initiative as part of their operational plans. 	<p>Jeremy Nurse Authority -> Decision Making -> Referral & Feedback</p> <p>Jeremy Nurse Authority -> Decision Making -> Referral & Feedback</p> <p>Jeremy Nurse Authority + Cross-Unit Structure (Vertical)</p> <p>Jeremy Nurse (1) Authority -> Resource Allocation -> Appointment, Leveraging Internal Capabilities, External Consultants + (2) Cross-Unit Structure -> Vertical -> Department</p> <p>Jeremy Nurse Cross-Unit Structure (Vertical + Horizontal)</p> <p>Jeremy Nurse DHQ: Communication -> Inclusion -> Strategic Planning</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What mechanisms / integrative devices are put in place to ensure that cross-unit collaboration successfully occurs in this specific initiative? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Making the OHQ actively part of the strategic planning process (e.g. market research) providing real time feedback which ensures engagement. For example, we are taking operating company executives with the DHQ team to visit potential own brands partners. ○ Developing a communication plan on the ongoing progress of this initiative. Part of the design of this communication plan is creating different messages for different audiences. ○ Conducting training sessions with external consultants with participants from across multiple Retail businesses. 	<p>Jeremy Nurse Communication</p> <p>Jeremy Nurse DHQ: Sensitization -> Communications Tools & Materials</p> <p>Jeremy Nurse Cross-Unit Structure (Vertical + Horizontal)</p> <p>Jeremy Nurse DHQ: Socialization -> Induction -> Training & Education</p>

Source: Author’s Field Notes

The second feature is that all final codes were elaborated to three distinct levels. For example, “Authority -> Decision Making -> Referral & Feedback” was assigned to the first coded statements from the top. This meant that the theoretical concept of Authority as an integrative device was recognized as being at play, but I also created elaboration constructs to two further levels, that is, Decision Making and Referral & Feedback, representing more specific manifestations of the integrative devices in practice within the case study

research setting. I will provide more insight into the analysis and results yielded from this elaboration process in the next chapter.

Data organization and analytical tools

After coding was finalized, I commenced a process of frequency tabulation for all the parenting propositions and integrative devices recorded in the field notes. The data was organized in Microsoft Excel eventually resulting in 10 cross-tabulation matrices for both the parenting propositions and integrative devices by case. I utilized the conditional formatting and other tools in Excel to perform analysis of the frequencies to help elucidate with initial insights to support sensemaking of the vast amount of data that was collected.

As it relates to the integrative devices specifically, I used *issue trees* (Conn & McLean, 2019) to illustrate and disaggregate the elaborations from the existing theoretical concepts into specific *HQ roles* and further into *operating manifestations* undertaken by the management. It should be noted that these issues trees will be a key feature of the write-ups for each case in Chapter Four. Additionally, I used both primary and secondary data sources to develop narratives of each case that further elaborated the context and served as a rich analytical foundation for the elaboration of existing theoretical concepts. The final report of my conclusions from these results is included in Chapter Five.

Issues of Trustworthiness

In quantitative research, the standards used for evaluating the quality of studies evolve around criteria such as internal validity, external validity, reliability, and objectivity (Trochim & Donnelly, 2008). However, with qualitative research, the

notion of *trustworthiness* is more central and involves issues such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Bryman, 2004). Table 3.2 shows four trustworthiness criteria and associated evidence surrounding how I have sought to satisfy each criterion in my research.

Table 3.2: Trustworthiness Criteria and Evidence

Traditional Criteria	Trustworthiness Criteria	Evidenced in this study by:
Internal Validity	Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Theory elaboration approach leveraging existing concepts to support coding, analysis, and interpretation of findings. ▪ Triangulation: semi-structured interviews, internal company documents, public filings. ▪ Transparent and clear chain of evidence. ▪ Self-reflections as an insider; ability to collect data and access key informants. ▪ Multiple data analysis techniques.
External Validity	Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple case study within one large organization. ▪ Within case and across case analyses. ▪ Solid rationale for case selection: why these five cases were selected given the research question. ▪ Manifestation of general strategic problems (corporate strategy – Goold & Campbell (2002a); organizational integration – Castañer & Ketokivi (2018).
Reliability	Dependability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Alignment between research questions and methodological modality. ▪ Theoretical sampling. ▪ Interview protocol developed. ▪ Data storage and management - how data was organized, stored, and managed (Excel, Word, Dropbox).

Traditional Criteria	Trustworthiness Criteria	Evidenced in this study by:
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Case study organization revealed – Massy is a publicly trading company with financial, strategic, and other information made available online.
Objectivity	Confirmability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Structured data management. ▪ Contemporaneous field notes. ▪ Back-up records of interview data.

Source: Bloomberg & Volpe (2016), Author's Analysis

Ethical considerations

Use of informants in empirical research is associated with a number of ethical considerations (Bryman, 2004). According to Diener and Crandall (1978), some of the main areas to be addressed with respect to ethics are harming participants, informed consent, as well as privacy and confidentiality issues.

Insofar as potential harm to participants was concerned, I sought to maintain confidentiality and anonymity of all informants. This was the main reason for not recording the interviews and to review my contemporaneous notes with the interviewee before terminating the interview. Secondly, I ensured that the decision to participate in the interviews was indeed voluntary. To ensure this, I decided not to interview any informants who could be construed in any way to be my subordinate. Of course, I interviewed several managers and officers who had a lower rank than me, but I ensured that there was no direct or indirect vertical relationship with these informants as I wanted to avoid informants that would in any way feel that they are beholden to me.

While the name of the case study organization has been made public, I kept the names and identities of all informants confidential as indicated to them in the respective interviews. Moreover, confidential data and information collected from the interviews were placed in cloud storage only accessible by me, my doctoral advisor, and research assistants when required. Independent of this study, I am contractually bound as an executive to protect and keep confidential highly sensitive information. As a board member of several Massy subsidiaries, I also owe the legal fiduciary duty of loyalty and care to these companies.

In summary, I wish to acknowledge that while being a corporate insider bestows my research with many advantages, it also raises a few ethical considerations that I have taken into account in how I conducted the study. Most importantly, I must be continuously mindful of what is appropriate not only in respect to ethics, but also in the legal sense. Disclosing privileged information would be not only unethical, but it can also constitute a breach of my fiduciary duties.

Summary

In this chapter, I presented my research design based on the multiple case study methodology to support theory elaboration on the role that HQ plays in cross-unit collaboration, and how specifically this form of collaboration can be achieved via the deployment of integrative devices. Five cases were selected from within Massy, the key sampling criteria being the HQ level of origination and the contextual occurrence of cross-unit collaboration as part of an organizational initiative. I selected 55 informants based on their direct involvement and knowledge of the specific cases.

My main method of data collection was with in-depth semi-structured interviews, and I also used internal company documents and publicly available information as secondary data sources. My analytical process, which was iterative, involved frequency tabulations, issue tree analysis, case narrative development, and comparative case analysis for pattern matching or contrasting. Lastly, I have offered self-reflections as a corporate insider.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS & INTERPRETATION

Introduction

This chapter presents the key findings, supporting analyses and interpretations arising out of the insights attained from the interviews conducted, and the structure of the chapter is explained below. After this introduction, I continue with a section that provides additional insight on Massy, particularly in relation to the general role of HQ apparent within the firm, based on the collective perceptions of the informants. My rationale for including this section is that further enriching our comprehension of the firm's overall parenting philosophy can serve to answer the research questions in a more contextualized manner.

In the third section of this chapter, I present the findings associated with each of the five cases including detailed narratives of what I discovered leveraging the analytical tools such as cross-tabulated data matrices and issue trees. The last section of the chapter includes analyses across the cases, offering comparative and contrasting perspectives with respect to the research findings.

Case Contextual Insights on the General Role of HQ

I applied Goold & Campbell's (2002b) parenting propositions to code the transcribed responses in the field notes from the first two questions in my interview protocol. These propositions have been described by Goold & Campbell (2002b) as the ways in which parent entities endeavor to create value from how they manage the subunits under their purview (see Table 4.1 for a description of the parenting proposition, with examples).

Table 4.1: Descriptions of the Five Parenting Propositions

Parenting Proposition	Descriptor
Select	<p><i>How value is created:</i> This involves the acquisition or disposal of units to optimize value for the overall firm.</p> <p><i>Examples:</i> Acquisitions, divestitures, joint ventures.</p>
Build	<p><i>How value is created:</i> This proposition involves the parent organization assisting the units to expand their scale and scope.</p> <p><i>Examples:</i> Expansion into new territories; product range extensions.</p>
Stretch	<p><i>How value is created:</i> This proposition involves parent intervention to enhance value by optimizing costs, supporting organic revenue growth, and improving quality or standards.</p> <p><i>Examples:</i> Stretch targets, benchmarking.</p>
Link	<p><i>How value is created:</i> This involves the parent helping the units to work together on initiatives that they would not naturally collaborate on voluntarily or find it difficult to do so.</p> <p><i>Examples:</i> Centralization, enterprise-wide collaborative projects.</p>
Leverage	<p><i>How value is created:</i> This proposition involves the parent exploiting a central resource, which could be tangible or intangible in nature.</p> <p><i>Examples:</i> Shared services, intellectual property management (e.g. patents), global business development.</p>

Source: Goold & Campbell (2002a), Goold & Campbell (2002b), Author's synthesis

From analyzing the data derived and presented from the coded field notes leveraging the parenting propositions, some key insights are revealed with respect to the general role HQ within Massy at the time the study was conducted. The results represented in Figure 4.1 are shown by each HQ level represented by the collective set of informants as well as the total across all levels. The total across all HQ levels is equivalent to the total across all cases, and it should be noted that the first two interview questions were positioned as

general queries about the role of HQ at all levels within the firm, and not specific to the case to which the respective informants were assigned.

From the 55 interviews I conducted, there were a total of 379 parenting proposition codes assigned from the responses transcribed into field notes, with 294 and 85 codes associated with Interview Question 1 (What are the various roles of HQ in the Group?) and Interview Question 2 (What role does HQ play in supporting cross-unit collaboration?), respectively. For Interview Question 1, the top three parenting propositions in aggregate represented 86% of the codes with Stretch, Leverage and Link ranked in order of the highest frequency. Select and Build together made up the remaining 14%.

For Interview Question 2, Stretch, Leverage and Link were also the top three propositions representing in aggregate 98.8% of the 85 codes. In this case, the ranking order was different with Link representing 60% of the parenting proposition codes, Stretch representing 29.4% and Leverage at 9.4%. Build garnered merely one coded response and Select yielded none, across all HQ informant levels.

Figure 4.1: Data Matrix - Figure Frequencies of Parenting Propositions

Coded by HQ Level of Informant for Interview Questions 1 and 2

Frequency of PP* Codes by HQ Level of Informant (Question 1)	Q1: What are the various roles of HQ in the Group? (Absolute Frequencies)					Q1: What are the various roles of HQ in the Group? (PP* % Contribution by Level)						
	Select	Build	Stretch	Link	Leverage	All PPs	Select	Build	Stretch	Link	Leverage	All PPs
CHQ	3	2	29	5	18	57	5.3%	3.5%	50.9%	8.8%	31.6%	100.0%
DHQ	11	8	60	5	23	107	10.3%	7.5%	56.1%	4.7%	21.5%	100.0%
OHQ	8	8	68	19	27	130	6.2%	6.2%	52.3%	14.6%	20.8%	100.0%
All Cases	22	18	157	29	68	294	7.5%	6.1%	53.4%	9.9%	23.1%	100.0%
Frequency of PP* Codes by HQ Level of Informant (Question 2)	Q2: What role does HQ play in supporting cross-unit collaboration? (Absolute Frequencies)					Q2: What role does HQ play in supporting cross-unit collaboration? (PP* % Contribution by Level)						
	Select	Build	Stretch	Link	Leverage	All PPs	Select	Build	Stretch	Link	Leverage	All PPs
CHQ	0	0	5	11	2	18	0.0%	0.0%	27.8%	61.1%	11.1%	100.0%
DHQ	0	1	11	20	3	35	0.0%	2.9%	31.4%	57.1%	8.6%	100.0%
OHQ	0	0	9	20	3	32	0.0%	0.0%	28.1%	62.5%	9.4%	100.0%
All Cases	0	1	25	51	8	85	0.0%	1.2%	29.4%	60.0%	9.4%	100.0%

*Parenting Propositions

Source: Author's analysis

The first major finding arising directly from the data analysis above is that the general role of HQ in Massy is primarily focused on activities that are forms of Stretch, Leverage and Link parenting propositions individually or in combination. These three propositions are utilized the most frequently across all HQ levels in

general as well as in relation to cross-unit collaboration. This is substantiated by the very little variation in the distribution of frequencies across all three HQ levels and for the totals for both Interview Questions 1 and 2, as illustrated by Figure 4.1.

My interpretation of this finding is intricately connected to the evolutionary context of Massy at the time the study was conducted. Figure 4.2 shows the evolution of the company's after-tax profit performance from 1968 to 2021 and it highlights some key events along this timeline. I will focus on the period from 2014 onwards as I was officially enrolled in the doctoral program in 2015, and the core part of my research was conducted during the latter years of this timeline.

As Figure 4.2 shows, there were significant profit declines in financial years 2016 and 2017 mainly due to major economic slowdowns in two key geographic markets (i.e., Trinidad & Tobago and Barbados), substantial losses on disposing underperforming companies, and the negative one-off impact on the property and casualty insurance business associated with three major hurricanes that hit the region (Massy, 2016; Massy, 2017).

Figure 4.2: Massy's Profit After Tax and Business Evolution, 1968-2021

Source: Extracted from Massy Group CEO's Presentation to Jamaica Stock Exchange, January 2022

During this period of profit decline, there was also a notable increase in focus across the Group on cost containment and efficiency. In the company's annual reports from 2016 to 2018, the updates from the Group CEO gave clear signals that these areas were strategically important.

“In FY 2017, the Group will pursue a number of continuous improvement initiatives and methodologies, focused on process redesign and other methodologies to continuously maintain a lean, focused organisation. Kaizen principles and Process Redesign are being taught throughout the Group to launch a re-examination of our processes and ways of doing business to eliminate waste, frustration and unnecessary cost.”

Group CEO's Report, (Massy, 2016)

“In the latter part of the financial year we identified a major opportunity to achieve greater efficiency and cost compression through the implementation of global best practices in procurement. This effort positions us to achieve a number of objectives in the following financial year and in years to come, including achieving industry cost leadership and strengthening Massy's competitiveness; increasing the safety and quality of products and services we provide to our customers; sourcing best-in-class products and services for our Group companies and developing new competencies and capabilities. We conducted an internal recruitment drive to dedicate full time resources to the initiative, which will focus on specific categories within our operations, facilitated by expert consultants and with support from business users across the Group. We expect that new projects and processes, such as leveraging our supplier base for improved volume pricing, will emerge from this procurement exercise in the second quarter of the following year and beyond.”

Group CEO's Report, (Massy, 2017)

“We recognise the importance of leveraging economies of scale in operations expertise, systems integration and processes and innovations across a more focused set of activities Other Group Strategies include a diagnostic to explore the options for radically improving the operations efficiency of the Group by reengineering processes, establishing common operating platforms and evaluating different shared service centre designs to gain efficiency from common administrative processes across the Group.”

Letter from the Group CEO, (Massy, 2018)

The financial performance of the firm started to recover in 2018 (Massy, 2018) and notably, a major strategic intervention occurred subsequently in 2019. The

intervention eventually resulted in a decision by the Group CEO and his senior executive team, supported by the parent company Board, to focus the Group around three main industry segments. This decision was further solidified with the implementation of a new governance structure that promoted the devolution of autonomy from the CHQ to the leadership teams of these segments (Massy, 2019).

Updates from both the Chairman and Group CEO in 2019 and 2020 provide key insights on this strategic transformation.

“The executives in the portfolios are being given greater autonomy with an increased delegation of authority going to the portfolio boards and Chairmen than in the past. With this change and the focus of portfolio executives on the specific activities of their portfolios and not on Group initiatives, Massy’s structure will become more like a true investment holding structure with strong, distinct portfolios, focused on the industries in which Massy has its greatest strengths.”

Letter from the Chairman, (Massy, 2019)

“To assure our future, we need to focus on our key verticals and become increasingly more expert, more competitive and more performance oriented. To facilitate this, the Group has reorganised itself around three main industry Portfolios and will transfer greater autonomy to the executives operating these Portfolios. We expect them to focus more intently on building distinctive capability, to drive innovation within the business and to effect strategies more directly on trends, opportunities and threats; and to better identify and mitigate risks specific to those portfolios The three main Portfolios were selected after a process of assessing the competence and capabilities in all of our Business Units and identifying the most significant and credible growth opportunities. The three main Portfolios identified are: Integrated Retail, Motors and Machines, and Gas Products”

Letter from the Group CEO, (Massy, 2019)

“Good corporate governance is always at the fore of our leaders’ minds as we consider ways to strive for continuous improvement in our governance and leadership. Enhanced focus placed on strengthening the governance of boards for the Group’s main Portfolios (Integrated Retail, Motors & Machines and Gas Products) has served us well during this COVID-19 pandemic. It was quite fortuitous that the Group had already implemented the governance enhancements within its Portfolios when the pandemic hit. The businesses

were well positioned to act with pace, agility and autonomy. Massy was able to emerge and move as a stronger, faster and more streamlined Group of businesses.

The Portfolio boards were strengthened in various ways including introducing Independent Directors on these boards. Each Portfolio board now has an equal number on Independent and Executive board members. Some of the Independent board members are experts in specialised business areas and some were selected from the Massy Holdings board. All Portfolio directors were provided with an induction and training specific to the roles of directors on the Portfolio boards.

Board audit and risk committees were established within each Portfolio in order to ensure greater focus on audit and risk matters. The parent board Audit & Risk Committee then supported a process that led the Group through a risk reset exercise which clarified and highlighted the varying areas of risk priority, mitigation and appetite across businesses in each Portfolio and across the various territories within which the Group operates. This strengthening of the Group's risk management framework underpins the autonomy and agility that now exists across the Portfolios."

Letter from the Chairman, (Massy, 2020)

The financial year 2019 clearly marked the beginning of Massy's transformation from a traditional conglomerate to more of an investment holding company (Massy, 2019; Massy, 2020). From an organization design perspective, the firm embarked on changing its operating model to one that can be described as decentralization with coordinated control (Garvin & Levesque, 2006).

My perspective is that this evolutionary context which started with a state of the business experiencing economic turbulence in key territories, followed by financial performance challenges, which then promulgated an increased focus on cost containment. Thereafter, a decision on a major strategic transformation to decentralization with coordinated control during a recovery period, collectively in this chronological order, drove the need for HQ at all levels to be primarily internally focused. Therefore, it makes sense that the parenting propositions

that would have been more prominent in this evolving context are those more predisposed to supporting the optimization of the existing portfolio of units.

By their definitions as per Table 4.1 above, ‘Stretching’, ‘Leveraging’ and ‘Linking’ would better align with the predisposition of HQ to search for value creation internally via extracting greater efficiencies from the existing portfolio units. This compares to ‘Selecting’ and ‘Building’ propositions where HQ would be typically more focused on creating additional value by transforming the scope of the units or the entire firm.

The second finding is that each of the parenting propositions primarily manifests in specific forms of HQ roles both in general and specifically in relation to cross-unit collaboration. In the case of Stretch, it manifests primarily as *setting governance standards* and *initializing performance targets*. For Leverage, two manifestations stood out which were seeking *economies of scale and scope* and *capitalizing on internal talent and capabilities*. As it relates to Link, *fostering internal communities* and *strategic planning* were the two main manifestations.

Tables 4.2 and 4.3 illustrate how some of the informants expressed their views on the various roles of HQ categorized by the three main propositions and manifestations based on responses to Interview Questions 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 4.2: Sample of Representative Informant Responses, Interview Question 1: What are the various roles of HQ in the Group?

Parenting Proposition	Manifestation	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
Stretch	Setting Governance Standards	<i>Another role of HQ is ensuring that “organizations don’t have to reinvent the wheel” by putting standardized policies and procedures in place. [Manager; CHQ]</i>

Parenting Proposition	Manifestation	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
		<p><i>One of the key roles would be policy development. The businesses obviously need governance of their operations which require standard operating procedures. We operate in multiple territories and multiple industries, so “structure is critical, so that the Group has a common identity”. [Manager; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Governance – creating consistent policies that govern the overall Group. Developing Group policies in areas such as HR and IT - “We have some broad guidelines, but it is not totally encompassing”. [CEO; OHQ]</i></p>
Stretch	Initializing Performance Targets	<p><i>Sets KPIs within their respective span of control to deliver against the Group strategic priorities. [Corporate Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Largely responsible for performance management of the operating companies within their span of control. “Pushing for performance” includes cost reduction, acquisitions, etc - “how can we grow the business” and improve profitability. [EVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>To give each subsidiary a “little push to help them to grow and stretch the boundaries of how they see things”. [Manager; OHQ]</i></p>
Leverage	Seeking Economies of Scale & Scope	<p><i>The various levels of HQ are also responsible for bringing a level of efficiency across the units by ensuring that functions are not duplicated. HQ identifies opportunities for centralization of functions (e.g. HR, IT, Marketing). [Corporate Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Understanding the opportunity that is available from amalgamating the volumes and experiences in the respective operating companies in order to leverage value, best practices and economies of scale, while leaving the OHQs local in their delivery. [SVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>For example, Massy Stores exist in 5 countries as a result of a history of acquisitions and a legacy of running businesses autonomously in each country. “If you want to get synergies and economies of scale, the individual countries are not going to do it on their own”. Therefore, the DHQ acts at a higher level “to bring all those individual OHQs together” to ensure that strategies are aligned and to leverage certain aspects across all geographic markets. [Director; OHQ]</i></p>
Leverage	Capitalizing on Internal Talent & Capabilities	<p><i>Providing functional support services (e.g. Legal, Finance, HR) to the entire Group. [SVP; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The HQ provides strategic and operational support to the businesses when needed. For example, a Business Development Analyst being assigned to provide direct data analysis support for organizational restructuring. [Analyst; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>From a country perspective, the DHQ interfaces with the Government and other key external stakeholders to help support corporate objectives as well as operating</i></p>

Parenting Proposition	Manifestation	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
		<i>company objectives unique to each respective business. [Managing Director; OHQ]</i>
Link	Fostering Internal Communities	<p><i>One of the main roles of the CHQ is to be the central point of coordination, control and collaboration - “Let’s bring you guys together”. Control is not meant to be “command and control”. It is meant to be facilitation. For example, “Yesterday, I facilitated a meeting that brought together ITC, Retail and Energy together” which started as an IT conversation in one area and was extended to other areas. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The DHQ executives talk to each other and organically collaborate on areas of opportunity between their businesses. Lots of these collaborations occur informally at various meetings (e.g. Executive Committee and Investment Committee Meetings). [Analyst; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Creating forums with diverse participants to collaborate and synergize in the development of new ideas (e.g. Massy Innovation Tournament). “We actually created a new product – a mobile service” coming out of the Massy Innovation Tournament. [CEO; OHQ]</i></p>
Link	Strategic Planning	<p><i>When we rebranded at Massy, our Group CEO mentioned that there are different roles that HQ can play. He saw that the role of the HQ would be the “Evangelical Architect” which speaks to helping the businesses to “construct the future” by connecting the dots to create new opportunities that did not exist before. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>“The operating companies are doing things differently, but they are in the same business”. Therefore, the role of the DHQ is to find best practices across the region. (e.g. Category Management in Retail – Massy Stores (St. Lucia) has better instituted category management practices compared to the other markets, and we are leveraging that experience to see how we can implement in the other markets). [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Sharing, brainstorming and strategizing with other DHQs to achieve desired outcomes (e.g. efficiency, cost reduction). [CEO; OHQ]</i></p>

Source: Author’s field notes and coding analysis

Table 4.3: Sample of Representative Informant Responses, Interview Question

2: What role does HQ play in supporting cross-unit collaboration?

Parenting Proposition	Manifestation	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
Stretch	Setting Governance Standards	<p><i>The CHQ developed a compensation model (i.e. balanced scorecard) with a Group component – this can help to foster collaboration. [SVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Ensuring that functional areas (e.g. HR, Health, Safety, Security & Environment (HSSE), Finance, Customer Service) are aligned regionally in terms of how they operate. [SVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Establishing and sharing policies to ensure consistency in key areas (e.g. customer service). [Director; OHQ]</i></p>
Stretch	Initializing Performance Targets	<p><i>Through common requests, the various HQ levels tend “to force collaborative activities” across the various units within their respective spans of control. [EVP; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The various levels of HQ “set the tone” and “creates the space” to enable cross-unit collaboration. [Analyst; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>No major role in supporting collaboration apart from “setting the tone”. “The mandate to collaborate across business units – is set from the top – from the CHQ”. [Managing Director; OHQ]</i></p>
Leverage	Seeking Economies of Scale & Scope	<p><i>Take the medical plans for example. “Rather than have a series of medical plans with different benefits and costs across territories, it would be more cost efficient to have a Group medical plan that will draw upon economies of scale in producing enhanced benefits”. Therefore, it is HQ that facilitates the process of fostering Group integration. [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Identifying solutions and platforms that can be utilized by multiple businesses and countries (e.g. Implementation of Office 365 across the Massy Group). [Associate; DHQ]</i></p>
Leverage	Capitalizing on Internal Talent & Capabilities	<p><i>Collecting data and performing the analysis to initiate Group strategic projects that enhance efficiency such as Procurement and Shared Services. It would be more difficult to accomplish these initiatives without the CHQ. [Corporate Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The HQ supports cross-unit collaboration by utilizing talent from various parts of the organization based on economies of skills and experience. Human resources are assigned to provide services based on their unique competencies to the benefit of areas other than their day-to-day responsibilities. [General Manager; OHQ]</i></p>
Link	Fostering Internal Communities	<p><i>Creating forums (e.g. meetings in which the Group CEO pulls together several executives, Executive Committees, social functions such as executive lunches) to support cross-unit collaboration. [Corporate</i></p>

Parenting Proposition	Manifestation	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
		<p><i>Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Fund activities and lead Group-wide initiatives that inherently require collaboration (e.g. Massy Innovation Tournament). [EVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Provide outlets for cross-unit collaboration to occur (e.g. the Connectivity Conference for Corporate Rebranding). [Manager; OHQ]</i></p>
Link	Strategic Planning	<p><i>For example, take Massy OneTime - where a customer offering was developed involving automotive (i.e. selling cars), general finance (i.e. financing cars), insurance (i.e. insuring cars). The CHQ developed this ecosystem concept (idea generation) and it was left to the business units to implement, but there are still challenges. [SVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The DHQ identifies cross-unit collaborative opportunities, devise the strategy and then facilitate implementation of the collaboration. [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>For example, the Integrated Retail Business Unit's DHQ held and facilitated a strategic session at the beginning of the fiscal year identifying some growth opportunities between Distribution and Retail. [CEO; OHQ]</i></p>

Source: Author's field notes and coding analysis

The Select and Build propositions were significantly less prominent in frequency of occurrence relative to the other three and representing only 11% of the total coded transcriptions. Nonetheless, I still included Table 4.4 to be exhaustive with the provision of additional insights on the general role of HQ with respect to these propositions. The Select parenting proposition primarily manifested as *corporate development and executing divestitures*, while Build manifested as *geographic expansion and new business lines and extensions*.

Table 4.4: Sample of Representative Informant Responses, Interview

Questions 1 and 2 for Select and Build Propositions

Parenting Proposition	Manifestation	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
Select	Corporate Development	<p><i>Championing M&A to support growth – this should always be done at the various HQ levels, but “never at the operating level”. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Portfolio review and management - new business development, mergers and acquisitions. [EVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>HQ also plays a role in business development – concerned with growth including acquisitions, other forms of new business development. [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p>
Select	Executing Divestitures	<p><i>Reviewing existing businesses and seeking to “clean-up” legacy operations. [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>One another role of HQ is to determine “the type of organizations that should fit into the Group’s structure”. This may be driven by divestment or acquisition activities and it should be noted that portfolio management is happening at all organizational levels. [CEO; OHQ]</i></p>
Build	Geographic Expansion	<p><i>Capital allocation across the businesses and markets. The decision making for major business and market expansion is taking place at the CHQ. [EVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>For example, let’s consider our geographic distribution in the region. If we consider markets such as Trinidad & Tobago which are largely driven by the oil and gas industry, a drop in oil prices has negatively impacted that economy, and by extension our businesses. Therefore, in recent years, there has been a greater drive to diversify both geographically (e.g. Colombia) and by sector (e.g. renewable energy). [Manager; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Conducts new business development activities (e.g. exploring new export markets) to grow the company. [Managing Director; OHQ]</i></p>
Build	New Business Lines & Extensions	<p><i>Working with commercial teams for new business development – “looking at white spaces in the portfolio”. [Managing Director; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>“This involves looking for new products or markets to compete in and to drive additional business in existing lines of business”. [Managing Director; OHQ]</i></p>

Source: Author’s field notes and coding analysis

In summary, the analysis and findings in this section supported the discovery of some general parenting philosophies within the case setting. Given the

evolutionary context at the time the study was conducted, the informants' responses substantiated that the main HQ roles across all levels were internally focused primarily utilizing parenting propositions such as Stretch through setting governance standards and initializing performance targets, Leverage through seeking economies of scale and scope and capitalizing on internal talent and capabilities, and Link via fostering internal communities and strategic planning. As indicated above, the Select and Build propositions did not materialize as frequently as the others based on the informants' responses. However, when they did show up, the corresponding manifestations were corporate development and executing divestitures for Select, while for Build there was geographic expansion and new business lines and extensions.

This study is about better understanding the role that multiple HQ levels play in supporting cross-unit collaboration, and how integrative devices are deployed to achieve such collaboration. Now that we have a greater comprehension of the general role of HQ within Massy as the case study organization, I will delve deeper in the next section on the findings and interpretation related to the five cases individually. As indicated in the synopsis provided in Chapter Three, each case encompasses an initiative that is characterized by cross-unit collaboration involving multiple HQ levels.

As a final clarification, while the sampling of the five cases was not random and no statistical generalizations are obviously warranted, I maintain that the parenting propositions manifested by the five initiatives convey a sense of generality in that they do manifest some of the more general characteristics of

Massy as a corporation. If I were to pick another five strategic initiatives from the same period, I predict they would manifest similar parenting propositions.

Findings & Interpretation Within Case: Prologue

I decided to include this prologue to provide a few clarifying points on the following sections containing the individual within-case write-ups. Firstly, the findings and interpretations for each case were derived from the informants' responses to Interview Question 3 (What roles do/did the various levels of HQ (i.e. CHQ, DHQ, OHQ) play in this specific strategic initiative?) and Interview Question 4 (What mechanisms / integrative devices are put in place to ensure that cross-unit collaboration successfully occurs in this specific initiative?).

These questions were case specific unlike the first two interview questions which required responses on the general role of HQ in Massy and not directly in relation to the case to which the informants were assigned.

Secondly, while Interview Questions 1 and 3 are quite similar, I would like to highlight a key difference in the response protocol. That is, the interviewees were required to answer Interview Question 3 by providing responses on each HQ level, compared to Interview Question 1 which I allowed the informants the choice in responding either generally or by HQ level depending on their own perspectives on the role of HQ.

Thirdly, my approach to coding the responses to Interview Questions 3 and 4 involved the application of integrative devices (Castañer & Ketokivi, 2018), which can be described as tools or mechanisms that organizations put in place

to achieve some desired form of organizational integration (Lawrence & Lorsch, 1967). Table 4.5 provides descriptions of the seven integrative devices.

Table 4.5: Descriptions of the Seven Integrative Devices

Integrative Device	Descriptor
Authority	The use of authority involves the referral of a subordinate unit to a superior entity in an organization to achieve some desired form of integration.
Formalization	Formalization is typically about achieving alignment and governance standards of processes, policies, or systems across organizational subunits.
Cross-Unit Structure	Cross-unit structures can be permanent or temporary structural devices implemented to facilitate or promote collaboration between units. It should be noted that cross-unit structures are put in place to solve integration that can be characterized as vertical (i.e. across units at different organizational levels) or horizontal (across units at the same organizational level).
Communication	Communication as an integrative device is primarily about creating awareness of the organizational requirement and benefits associated with integration with targeted messaging to encourage the desired behaviors.
Collective Incentives	These are incentives put in place to encourage subunits to work together to achieve an integration objective that may not naturally occur without the associated reward.
Multi-skilling	Multi-skilling involves the utilization of specialists (e.g. on cross-functional teams) or generalists (e.g. as liaisons) to support organizational integration.
Socialization	Socialization as an integrative device is about designing, promoting, and inculcating social norms, belief systems, specific activities, and ways of behavior to intentionally support integration efforts.

Source: Castañer & Ketokivi (2018), Author's synthesis

The fourth point is that I applied issue trees (Conn & McLean, 2019) which synthesized the findings showing which integrative devices were present for

each case based on the aggregate responses from the coded field notes. Additionally, I went through a process of elaborating on the integrative devices that were coded in the field notes to another level which I termed as *HQ integration roles*. For the purposes of this study, I will define HQ integration roles as generalizations of the role that HQ levels play to achieve cross-unit collaboration in the case. Figure 4.3 provides a generic example of an issue tree.

Figure 4.3: Illustrative Issue Tree Diagram

Source: Author's analysis

The final clarifying point is related to how the frequencies of coded data were tabulated from the responses for the latter two interview questions. The matrix in Figure 4.4 shows the cross-tabulated frequencies of integrative device codes

across all cases. The configuration of Figure 4.4 arose from two key decisions I made in relation to executing the analysis. The first decision was that I aggregated the frequencies of integrative device codes derived from Interview Questions 3 and 4. The reason for this is that after eyeballing the data and undergoing an iterative coding process, I recognized that responses to both questions could have been credibly classified applying Castañer & Ketokivi's (2018) typology of integrative devices.

The second decision I made was to tabulate the coded frequencies of the first two levels only, which were the integrative devices along with the elaborations to HQ integration roles. While it may have been useful to further tabulate the coded frequencies associated with the operating mechanisms, I decided against it in collaboration with my advisor as I believed that addressing the first two levels would take me to a saturation point which would have garnered enough insight to answer the research questions.

As illustrated in Figure 4.4, there were a total of 396 integrative device codes assigned to the transcribed field notes associated with Interviews Questions 3 and 4 in aggregate for all cases. In the order from highest to the lowest frequencies for all the cases, Authority represented 35.4% of the integrative device codes, Communication at 28.8%, Formalization at 14.4%, Cross-Unit Structure at 13.6%, with Socialization, Multi-skilling and Collective Incentives together making up the remaining 7.8%. In terms of HQ levels, the CHQ represented 234 (or 59.1%) of the integrative device codes, DHQ at 129 (or 32.6%) and the OHQ at 33 (or 8.3%).

Findings & Interpretation Within Case: Guyana Retail Entry

As indicated in Chapter Three, this case involves the expansion of an existing business to a new geographic market. It surrounds the activities associated with how the company planned for its food retail business line, Massy Stores, to enter Guyana via new site development. The below extracts from Massy's 2016 Annual Report provide some additional context on this initiative.

“Macroeconomic conditions in Guyana were generally favourable for 2016. Growth in GDP was expected to be around 4 percent, among the highest in Latin America and the Caribbean. Public investment and the discovery of new gold mines aided in the expansion of economic activity. Monetary policy remained accommodative as lower prices for imported goods, including fuel, helped ease inflationary pressure. Our introduction of the first Massy Stores location to Guyana has redefined the retail landscape in the country. The new supermarket is a first of its kind in terms of layout, design and variety of offerings. A second store will be opened in the New Year.”

Chairman's Report, (Massy, 2016)

“In March this year, Massy Stores launched its first supermarket in Guyana – the Group's 47th store in the region. Located in Amazonia Mall, East Bank Demerara, the store offers 16,000 square feet of retail space, making it the largest supermarket in the country. At the close of the Financial Year (FY), the Group recorded a significant increase in the store's customer base. A second store is under construction at the East Coast MovieTowne Complex and scheduled for launch in 2017.”

Group CEO's Report, (Massy, 2016)

“Collaboration among key personnel in the Massy Stores regional network was instrumental in the preparation and successful launch of the new Massy Stores Supermarket in Guyana. Furthermore, during the Financial Year, more emphasis was placed on the alignment of best practices across the territories to improve operational efficiency. Cross-functional, regional teams were formed to work on key areas such as shrink and inventory management, category management, and store modernisations. Collaboration is one of Massy's core values, and will continue to be a cornerstone in the operation of our stores.”

Segment Reports, Integrated Retail, (Massy, 2016)

Findings

For the Guyana Retail Entry case, there were four informants, two from the DHQ and two from the OHQ levels. There was a total of 34 integrative device codes based on the informants' responses, and with respect to HQ levels assigned to these codes, the CHQ, DHQ and OHQ represented 2.9%, 64.7% and 32.4% of the total respectively (Figure 4.5). Regarding the integrative devices identified, Authority represented 44.1% of the total, Cross-Unit Structure - 32.4%, Communication - 11.8%, Formalization - 5.9% and Socialization - 5.9%.

Figure 4.5: Data Matrix on Frequencies of Integrative Devices and HQ Integration Roles Coded for the Guyana Retail Entry Case

HQ Level	Authority		Formalization	Communication		Cross-Unit Structure		Socialization	All Integrative Devices	% Contrib.
	Decision Making	Resource Allocation	Standardization	Inclusion	Sensitization	Vertical Coordination	Horizontal Coordination	Induction		
CHQ	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2.9%
DHQ	1	9	0	3	1	5	3	0	22	64.7%
OHQ	0	4	2	0	0	3	0	2	11	32.4%
Total	15		2	4		11		2	34	
% Contrib.	44.1%		5.9%	11.8%		32.4%		5.9%	100.0%	

Source: Author's analysis

Authority was elaborated into the HQ integration roles of *decision making* and *resource allocation*, Formalization into *standardization*, Communication into *inclusion* and *sensitization*, Cross-Unit Structure into *vertical coordination* and *horizontal coordination*, and Socialization into *induction*. The issue tree in Figure 4.6 provides a graphical representation of how the integrative devices that manifested in this case have been elaborated into HQ integration roles.

Figure 4.6: Issue Tree - Guyana Retail Entry

Source: Author's analysis

Based on the empirical observations and frequencies, I highlight two key findings from the Guyana Retail Entry case. The first is that the DHQ had the most significant role and involvement relative to the other HQ organizational levels. The second finding is that the use of authority manifesting as *resource allocation* together with cross-unit structure manifesting as *vertical coordination*, by both the DHQ and OHQ levels, were the main integrative devices deployed to support cross-unit collaboration and achieve the desired objective of the Guyana Retail Entry initiative. Table 4.6 below illustrates how the informants expressed their views focusing on the two main integrative devices utilized and their respective HQ integration roles highlighted in the second finding.

Table 4.6: Selected Informant Responses for Interview Questions 3 and 4 -
Main Integrative Devices Used in the Guyana Retail Entry Case

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
DHQ	Authority	Resource Allocation	<p><i>The DHQ appointed a Project Champion to lead this team – this person was the Managing Director of Massy Stores in St. Lucia. [Director; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The Guyana Country DHQ provided support and guidance on local market dynamics. The Retail Regional DHQ collaborated more specifically with various companies in Guyana to attain on-the-ground insights on food retail and consumer behavior – market research. [SVP; DHQ]</i></p>
OHQ	Authority	Resource Allocation	<p><i>As this was a new entity in Guyana, the Retail operating company in Trinidad provided some functional expertise and shared services (e.g. Finance, IT). [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Massy Stores (Trinidad) was leveraged to support execution for retail entry into Guyana. For example, “we had to hire a man on the ground” and this person came from the retail operations in Trinidad. [Director; OHQ]</i></p>
DHQ	Cross-Unit Structure	Vertical Coordination	<p><i>The SVP/Chairman of Retail was the Project Sponsor and was responsible for the overall initiative. A Project Team was created to support implementation which included a Project Leader (i.e. Managing Director - Massy Stores (St. Lucia) and a Project Coordinator (i.e. Regional Business Excellence Director – Integrated Retail Business Unit). [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The DHQ decided on an organizational structure that involved Massy Stores (Trinidad) providing functional support (e.g. IT, Finance) to the new Massy Stores (Guyana) operations. [Director; OHQ]</i></p>
OHQ	Cross-Unit Structure	Vertical Coordination	<p><i>The Massy Stores (Guyana) OHQ is in Massy Stores (Trinidad), which provides the requisite strategic and operational oversight. [SVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>“It’s an extension of the Trinidad operations, but it is in a different country, and managed by the CEO of Massy Stores (Trinidad)”. [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p>

Source: Author’s field notes and coding analysis

Interpretation

In relation to the first finding, it is clear from the data presented above in Figure 4.5, that the DHQ and OHQ were the two HQ levels with the most involvement. It should be noted that the CHQ played an important role in an earlier stage of the initiative, especially on decision making to grant the requisite approvals (e.g. capital expenditure required) as well as providing endorsement of the strategy

to pursue this opportunity. Therefore, based on the context of the case, it is not surprising that the CHQ did not feature materially in terms of involvement.

On the other hand, I did expect significant involvement from the DHQ level since the official activation of the project and subsequent implementation activities were driven by the Integrated Retail Business Unit. Massy is a diversified group of companies with several business units organized along industry lines (see Figure 3.2), so when there is a strategic initiative that is specific to a particular segment, the CHQ of Massy would typically devolve autonomy to the leadership of the business units to execute through their respective DHQs and OHQs.

It is important to appreciate that there were two DHQs involved in this case (i.e. Integrated Retail Business Unit and Guyana Country Office). The primary DHQ in this initiative was the Integrated Retail Business Unit which has strategic and financial oversight of the Massy Stores regional operations. However, at the time the study was conducted, there also existed a Guyana Country DHQ which offered some shared services to all the businesses in that territory. Therefore, when I use the acronym DHQ in this section, I am referring to the Integrated Retail Business Unit, and I will indicate explicitly when alluding to the Guyana Country DHQ.

The OHQ's involvement may not have been so obvious until we acknowledge that to set up a Massy Stores operation in Guyana, a new legal entity and operating company had to be created as it was not in existence prior to the initiative. Hence, the DHQ leveraged the infrastructure of its existing operating

companies to support the project, especially the Trinidad operation, which was geographically closer in proximity to Guyana compared to the other Massy Stores territories in Barbados, St. Lucia, and St. Vincent. Thus, the main involvement at the OHQ level was through Massy Stores Trinidad, which eventually had to act as the direct parent to Massy Stores Guyana in the initial stages of its operation.

The second finding conveys that the use of authority through resource allocation and cross-unit structure through vertical coordination are the primary drivers of cross-unit collaboration for this case. Starting with resource allocation, the focus was on ensuring that the requisite human resources from existing Massy operations were available and their internal capabilities appropriately leveraged to support the initiative. For example, the DHQ led by a SVP who was Project Sponsor selected key personnel to be part of the Project Team, including the appointment of an existing Massy Stores CEO to be Project Owner with accountability for implementation. Other key people on the Project Team included DHQ-level personnel with functional responsibilities (e.g. Property Development, Business Excellence, IT), as well as executives and managers from Massy Stores Trinidad's OHQ.

The example demonstrates how authority can be applied because of inherent organizational power dynamics. In other words, by virtue of the DHQ having power over its existing OHQs, it had the ability to effectively direct and influence them in utilizing operating company resources to support an initiative that was outside the typical scope of their businesses. In this case, the OHQs are charged with responsibility for day-to-day operations in their respective

territories, so diverting attention to help launch a supermarket in a new territory would not have been the norm.

The DHQ also identified other resources that were not selected to be part of the Project Team, and that it did not have direct power over due to different reporting lines, but whose contribution would have been valuable to support the successful execution of the project. A good example of this was the DHQ liaising with the Guyana Country DHQ to determine what in-country resources and capabilities could have been leveraged to support the project. Given that Guyana had a well-established IT shared services operation, the Country DHQ became critical for supporting the implementation of hardware, communications, and other technology infrastructure for the new retail business.

As Figure 3.3 illustrates, the Guyana Country Office does not report to the Integrated Retail Business Unit structure, and there is parity in seniority between the executives in charge of the project and the Guyana Country DHQ. Hence, the ability to allocate resources transpired through DHQ-DHQ negotiations in the form of influence via request compared to the DHQ-OHQ negotiations which would have been likely to be more of influence via persuasion.

On cross-unit structure, I previously stated that the primary HQ integration role associated with this device that manifested was *vertical coordination*. Here, I am compelled to note the inconsistencies in the definition of coordination in the general management literature (Castañer & Oliveira, 2020), and therefore based on this case study's organizational context, I define vertical coordination

as the process of organizing people or teams across multiple HQs on *different organizational levels* to achieve a desired objective. Similarly, horizontal coordination can be defined when the process involves organizing people and teams across multiple HQs that are on the *same organizational level*.

Vertical coordination was a critical activity of the DHQ as there was a requirement to coordinate activities that involved Massy Stores operating companies and other existing Massy operating companies. This vertical coordination was delivered through various structures or mechanisms such as the Project Steering Committee, Project Team, or its senior members like the Project Sponsor or Project Owner. Vertical coordination was also notably carried out through an operating company. As an example, since the organizational model was designed with the new Massy Stores Guyana being a branch of the Trinidad operation, vertical coordination between the Massy Stores Trinidad OHQ and the operating team for the new supermarket in Guyana became a regular activity.

It is noteworthy to mention that execution of vertical coordination activities was delegated from the DHQ to the OHQ of Massy Stores Trinidad, particularly in respect to the cross-business interactions between this entity and other Massy operating companies in Guyana. A case in point is Massy Stores Trinidad collaborating with Massy Distribution Guyana to attain a better understanding of consumer trends and commercial norms in activities related to supply chain management as an example. In its home country, Massy Stores Trinidad is a leading food retailer with long-standing operating experience working with a myriad of local full-service distribution companies, including Massy Distribution

Trinidad, as part of the typical food and consumer supply chain. Hence, this OHQ was able to effectively liaise and coordinate activities with Massy Distribution Guyana to support making the new store operational.

Closing Remarks

The Guyana Retail Entry case involved the creation of a new unit in a new geographic market, and the DHQ played the most significant role in the deployment of integrative devices to ensure cross-unit collaboration occurred to meet the desired overall objective. Authority (resource allocation) and cross-unit structure (vertical coordination) used in combination were the two main devices utilized by DHQ and OHQ.

It should be noted that the first Massy Stores supermarket in Guyana successfully opened in March 2016 (Massy, 2016) and by the end of 2022 there were a total of five Massy Stores locations in Guyana (Massy, 2022).

Findings & Interpretation Within Case: Own Brands

The Own Brands case concerns the Integrated Retail Business Unit's strategic intention to transition the management of a portfolio of brands (see Figure 3.4) from subsidiary-led to a more regional or business unit centric oversight organizational model. Extracts from Massy's 2018 and 2019 Annual Reports provide insight on this initiative:

“Continued strengthening of our business model with greater focus on integration between our Retail and Distribution businesses, particularly in the areas of direct procurement, own brands and operational efficiency.”

Segment Reports, Integrated Retail (Massy, 2018)

“We have renewed our focus on developing a robust Own Brands portfolio to expand our variety and offer quality products at affordable prices to enrich the lives of our consumers. Additionally, we continued to strengthen our relationships with local, regional and international suppliers to procure products at better prices, and have intensified our category management efforts with training and executing best practices regionally.”

Segment Reports, Integrated Retail (Massy, 2018)

“Controlling the supply chain is key to controlling cost in the business, and our approach continues to focus on three main aspects of this. We have been developing our Own Brands portfolio regionally by extending our product range particularly in high volume categories, redesigning labels to appeal to consumers and enhancing quality where necessary.”

Segment Reports, Integrated Retail (Massy, 2019)

Findings

For this case, there were seven informants, three from the DHQ level and four from the OHQ level. As Figure 4.7 shows, there were a total of 35 integrative device codes based on the informants’ responses, and with respect to HQ levels assigned to these codes, the CHQ, DHQ and OHQ represented 11.4%, 80.0% and 8.6% of the total respectively. Regarding the integrative devices identified, Authority represented 45.7% of the total, Communication - 34.3%, Cross-Unit Structure - 14.3%, Formalization - 2.9% and Socialization - 2.9%.

Figure 4.7: Data Matrix on Frequencies of Integrative Devices and HQ Integration Roles Coded for the Own Brands Case

HQ Level	Authority		Formalization	Communication		Cross-Unit Structure	Socialization	All Integrative Devices	% Contrib.
	Decision Making	Resource Allocation	Standardization	Inclusion	Sensitization	Vertical Coordination	Induction		
CHQ	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	4	11.4%
DHQ	1	9	1	8	3	5	1	28	80.0%
OHQ	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	8.6%
Total	16		1	12		5	1	35	
% Contrib.	45.7%		2.9%	34.3%		14.3%	2.9%	100.0%	

Source: Author’s analysis

Authority was elaborated into the HQ integration roles of *decision making* and *resource allocation*, Formalization into *standardization*, communication into *inclusion* and *sensitization*, cross-unit structure into *vertical coordination*, and Socialization into *induction*. The issue tree in Figure 4.8 provides a graphical representation of how the integrative devices that manifested in this case have been elaborated into respective HQ integration roles.

Figure 4.8: Issue Tree - Own Brands

Source: Author's analysis

Based on the empirical observations and frequencies, I highlight two key findings from the Own Brands case. The first is that the DHQ had the greatest involvement and hence was the main driver of this initiative compared to the other two HQ levels. The second finding is that the application of authority manifesting as *resource allocation* together with communication manifesting as *inclusion* were complementary integrative devices deployed to support cross-unit collaboration in the Own Brands case.

Table 4.7 below illustrates how the informants expressed their views focusing on these two main integrative devices utilized and their respective HQ integration roles highlighted in the second finding.

Table 4.7: Selected Informant Responses for Interview Questions 3 and 4 - Main Integrative Devices Utilized in the Own Brands Case

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
CHQ	Authority	Decision Making	<p><i>The CHQ “set the tone” and has a requirement for the business to spend more time in this area. [Managing Director; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The DHQ highlighted Own Brands as a strategic initiative and presented that to the CHQ. However, after recognizing that progress was slow with implementation, the CHQ (i.e. Group CEO) “became the driving force” behind ensuring that Own Brands remained a strategic priority for the Integrated Retail Business Unit and put pressure on the DHQ to implement faster. [Analyst; DHQ]</i></p>
DHQ	Authority	Decision Making	<p><i>Developed the Own Brands strategy and took it to the CHQ for feedback. [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p>
OHQ	Authority	Decision Making	<p><i>Based on customer feedback and in-market data, the operating companies provide recommendations to the DHQ for extensions of the portfolio. [Director; OHQ]</i></p>
DHQ	Authority	Resource Allocation	<p><i>Putting the structure (e.g. someone was appointed at the DHQ level to lead the initiative) in place to support the development and execution of the Own Brands strategy. [Manager; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Determined the organizational structure and appointed key executives (e.g. Regional Commercial Director – Own Brands) to directly support the development of the Own Brands portfolio. Identifying resources (e.g. internal human resources, external consultants and experts) to support the initiative regionally. [Managing Director; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Recognizing the capability gaps, the DHQ also hired an external consulting firm to provide the requisite support. [Analyst; DHQ]</i></p>
DHQ	Communication	Inclusion	<p><i>Key executives from the DHQ and the Retail operating companies made a trip to Texas for two main reasons: 1) Open “peoples’ eyes” on the possibilities for Own Brands by visiting key retail businesses in the US market; 2) To meet with a “Private Label House” company that can support the development of Own Brands. [Manager; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Making the OHQ actively part of the strategic planning process (e.g. market research) providing real time feedback which ensures engagement. For example, we are taking operating company executives with the DHQ team to visit potential own brands partners. [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p>

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
			<i>“There was a trip to Texas with the private label people, but no one from Distribution was briefed or asked to attend”. [Managing Director; OHQ]</i>

Source: Author’s field notes and coding analysis

Interpretation

Like the Guyana Retail Entry case, the Own Brands initiative originated at the DHQ and is contextually specific to the Integrated Retail Business Unit, so it is understandable why this HQ level played such a significant role as per the first finding. Additionally, given the historical context of the Own Brands being managed independently by their respective subsidiaries, it seems logical for the DHQ level, which had the purview of the total Integrated Retail Business Unit, to be able to identify opportunities across the businesses and by extension across the entire portfolio of Own Brands.

In the case profile from Chapter Three, I included Massy’s internal definitions associated with the three categories of Own Brands. These definitions indicate that the brands are either legally owned by Massy operating companies, or there is an exclusive arrangement to utilize brands not owned by Massy in specific markets. Therefore, because of these characteristics, I expected that specific OHQs of Massy Stores and Massy Distribution operating companies would naturally have some level of involvement with respect to decision making despite that the project originated at the DHQ level.

Given the nature of the initiative, there was no delegation of authority required for the CHQ to grant financial or other forms of approval. However, based on the insights provided by some of the informants in the first two rows of Table

4.7, it is evident that the CHQ intervened to encourage greater progress on the Own Brands initiative. Apart from this, the CHQ did not play any other major role.

As it relates to the second finding, resource allocation and inclusion were important integration roles played primarily by the DHQ. As this initiative required oversight across brands originating from different companies based in multiple territories, it was deemed critical to appoint an executive (i.e. Regional Commercial Director) to be responsible for project coordination, as well as further development and implementation of the Own Brands strategy. External consultants were also commissioned to provide support to the Regional Commercial Director as this was a new role and she did not have any support resources from inception. However, other Integrated Retail Business Unit divisional department resources (e.g. Strategy, Business Excellence) were leveraged to support the project when required.

While the DHQ directly appointed the Regional Commercial Director and external consultants, it was important for that HQ level to liaise with the OHQs to select key resources within the operating companies to work on the project based on their roles or institutional knowledge of the targeted brand and product portfolios. It should be noted that the Regional Commercial Director with support from internal resources and external consultants essentially acted as a structural integrative device in the form of a temporary project team that continuously activated collaboration between the DHQ and multiple OHQs.

Following from this, the application of inclusion of subsidiary stakeholders by the DHQ in key strategic activities was highly complementary to the use of authority manifesting as resource allocation. The key mechanisms associated with inclusion utilized were road shows/territory visits by the project team, special planning meetings and an overseas business trip to engage a strategic partner that was selected to help develop marketing, and brand management capabilities. All these activities had a common theme of bringing together key stakeholders from both the DHQ and OHQ for problem-solving and strategic planning. The objective in each case was to align on how the Integrated Retail Business Unit should better organize both regionally and in-territory to extract greater value from the Own Brands portfolio.

Closing Remarks

The Own Brands case involved a strategic initiative to reorganize the management of a portfolio of brands from being independently run by subsidiaries to a more centralized organizational oversight model. The DHQ level, where the initiative originated from, played the most significant role, with Authority (resource allocation) and Communication (inclusion) being the two main integrative devices utilized to support cross-unit collaboration in the effort to meet the desired objective. There were some successes derived from the Own Brands initiative, aptly articulated by a SVP involved in the initiative:

“The DHQ did influence the movement of some brands across countries. For example, the Cuisine, Price Saver and Hi-Dee brands which originated in Trinidad are now offered at Massy Stores in Barbados and St. Lucia, and Valrico which originated in Barbados is now represented by Massy Distribution in Trinidad and Jamaica.”

Informant: Senior Vice President

However, the Own Brands initiative as originally conceived was halted in the financial year 2020, as the Integrated Retail Business Unit transitioned to a more territory-centric organizational structure to better align with its updated strategic priorities.

Findings & Interpretation Within Case: Corporate Rebranding

Corporate Rebranding was one of the most transformative initiatives in the history of Massy because of the resultant change in long-standing brand identifies of many subsidiaries operating in several industries and geographic markets. This case is about the planning and execution activities surrounding the initiative, which required a considerable amount of collaboration across the total Massy enterprise, with the involvement of employees from multiple businesses, territories, and organizational levels. Extracts from the 2014 and 2015 Annual Reports provide additional insight:

“Within the Massy Board and among Executives, there is a shared conviction that the rebranding marks an unqualified advance, justifying the investment in making it happen. Internally, it makes a positive difference that 10,000+ people, who, were once identified with separate and distinct subsidiaries, now feel a sense of belonging to a single, all encompassing, Massy Family. As exciting new possibilities open up for collaboration and sharing within the Massy Group “ecosystems”, fresh energy has been released, capable of moving the whole Group progressively forward.

Externally, customers are encouraged to see the Group’s capacity to offer a broad spectrum of solutions. As customers expectations are raised, the Massy Group must meet the challenge of upgrading the quality of service offered especially by companies dealing with the public, all now bearing the Massy brand. Great effort is being devoted to improving the quality of customer service at all Massy companies, particularly the consumer-facing companies.”

Chairman’s Report (Massy, 2014)

“Consideration was given to completely new names and to retaining the name Neal & Massy across the entire Group. A strong consensus among the Board and Management was that a change of name was needed to signal the change in strategy and management approach towards greater collaboration across the

Group. Several completely different names were entertained but there was an unforeseen pull towards Massy.

Many people in Trinidad and Tobago had already abbreviated Neal & Massy to “Massy” for several years and it preserved our linkage to the heritage of the two founding fathers: Harry Neal and Charles Massy. The obvious downside was the dropping of “Neal”. After much deliberation, we aligned on “Massy” the best of all alternatives considered and gave design instructions to ensure that the “N” and the “M” from “Neal” and “Massy” should be clearly evident in the design of the logo.”

Group CEO’s Report (Massy, 2014)

“We have seen the transformation to have the widely positive effect of ‘uncomplicating’ our lives, clarifying the Group’s image, reshaping impressions retained by the general public, and of liberating energies to be more and do more. With Massy as the corporate brand, we successfully renamed all companies with key sub-brands which signify the core businesses.

Massy Motors, Massy Stores, Massy United Insurance and Massy Finance are the key sub-brands for our consumer-facing portfolio. Massy Distribution, Massy Trading, Massy Technologies, Massy Energy, Massy Gas Products, Massy Machinery, Massy Pres-T-Con are the key sub-brands for our business-to-business portfolio.”

Group CEO’s Report (Massy, 2014)

“2015 marked a full year of operating with a new brand, Massy, which helped us to refine our identity to better deliver on our strategy. We continue to pursue greater integration within the Massy Group to uncomplicate the lives of the people we serve in the territories in which we operate. Our brand promise is to make things easy again: easier to buy, easier to own, easier to use and, ultimately, easier to enjoy and we want to remove the barriers that make life complicated.

To deliver on that brand promise, we shared accountability across all businesses and shared collaboration among our leadership, which was unprecedented. Unified with a common purpose of ‘creating value, transforming life,’ we were guided by our values of honesty and integrity, responsibility, growth and continuous improvement, collaboration and love and care to deliver on our brand promise.”

Group CEO’s Report (Massy, 2015)

Findings

For this case, there were 14 informants, three from the CHQ level, five from the DHQ level, and six from the OHQ level. As Figure 4.9 illustrates, there were a

total of 121 integrative device codes based on the informants' responses, and with respect to HQ levels assigned to these codes, the CHQ, DHQ and OHQ represented 70.2%, 21.5% and 8.3% of the total respectively. Regarding the integrative devices identified, Communication represented 35.5% of the total, Authority - 33.9%, Socialization - 14%, Cross-Unit Structure - 9.9%, Formalization - 5.8% and Multi-skilling - 0.8%.

Figure 4.9: Data Matrix on Frequencies of Integrative Devices and HQ Integration Roles Coded for the Corporate Rebranding Case

HQ Level	Authority			Formalization		Communication			Cross-Unit Structure		Socialization		Multi-Skilling	All Integrative Devices	% Contrib.
	Decision Making	Resource Allocation	Intermediation	Governance	Standardization	Inclusion	Translation	Sensitization	Vertical Coordination	Horizontal Coordination	Induction	Participation	Managerial Transfer		
CHQ	16	8	1	0	5	15	0	15	8	1	0	15	1	85	70.2%
DHQ	1	2	12	1	1	1	2	3	1	0	1	1	0	26	21.5%
OHQ	1	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	10	8.3%
Total	41			7		43			12		17		1	121	
% Contrib.	33.9%			5.8%		35.5%			9.9%		14.0%		0.8%	100.0%	

Source: Author's analysis

Communication was elaborated into the HQ integration roles of *inclusion*, *translation* and *sensitization*, Authority into *decision making*, *resource allocation* and *intermediation*, Socialization into *induction* and *participation*, Cross-Unit Structure into *vertical coordination* and *horizontal coordination*, Formalization into *governance* and *standardization*, and Multi-skilling to *managerial transfer*. The issue tree in Figure 4.10 provides a graphical representation of how the integrative devices that manifested in this case have been elaborated into respective HQ integration roles.

Figure 4.10: Issue Tree - Corporate Rebranding

Source: Author's analysis

Based on the empirical observations and frequencies, I highlight three key findings from the Corporate Rebranding case. The first finding is that the CHQ was the main driver of this initiative supported by the DHQs in coordinating specific activities as per guidance by the CHQ in their respective areas of control and responsibility. The second finding is that the use of authority manifesting as *decision making* primarily at the CHQ level, and Authority manifesting as *intermediation* exhibited by the various DHQs were both critical in ensuring collaboration occurred in the effort to meet the desired objective.

The third finding is that the use of communication manifesting as *inclusion* and *sensitization*, and Socialization manifesting as *participation* were together also

major integrative devices deployed to support cross-unit collaboration to ultimately get all key internal stakeholders onboard and aligned with implementing the Corporate Rebranding initiative. Table 4.8 illustrates how the informants expressed their views focusing on the main integrative devices utilized and their respective HQ integration roles observed.

Table 4.8: Selected Informant Responses for Interview Questions 3 and 4 - Main Integrative Devices Utilized in the Corporate Rebranding Case

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
CHQ	Authority	Decision Making	<p>Made the decision to rebrand and set the vision and strategy behind the Corporate Rebranding initiative. The CHQ spent a lot of time getting alignment from the various Business Unit Chairman – “getting people on board”. [Manager; CHQ]</p> <p>Conceptualized the vision and idea for the “rebranding story”. The CHQ set the agenda (e.g. timelines) for the broad program of rebranding across the entire Group. The main agenda item was “this is what we want it to look like and what we want to achieve”. [Manager; DHQ]</p> <p>“This is where it was envisioned, this is where it was created and rightly so”. The rebranding architecture and setting of standards occurred at the CHQ. [SVP; CHQ]</p> <p>The CHQ was responsible for making the decision to rebrand. Put aside the budget – “it was damn expensive”. [CEO; OHQ]</p>
DHQ	Authority	Intermediation	<p>Organized execution at the country level based on requirements set by the CHQ. [General Manager; OHQ]</p> <p>After the Connectivity Conference, the DHQ really got involved to prepare for execution with their respective operating companies. [EVP; DHQ]</p> <p>The Country DHQ in Barbados played an important role in bringing internal stakeholders together to solve logistical problems and get alignment on communication. The Business Unit Chairman played a similar role by bring the executives from the various operating companies together to discuss and solve problems associated with regional alignment. The DHQs main role was to ensuring coordination and execution according to stipulated deadlines. [Director; OHQ]</p>
CHQ	Communication	Inclusion	<p>The Connectivity Conference in 2014 held in Barbados – this was when the brand was officially revealed to ~200 Massy key executives. This was when the expectations of the “ONE Massy” concept was shared and discussed. In this session, we also voted on selecting the new core values and held break-out sessions to brainstorm on ecosystems and how they could work. [Manager; CHQ]</p> <p>CHQ executives took the time to be “physically present” visiting the various territories, meeting and working with the</p>

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
			<p><i>local executives to build relationships and establish trust. [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Connectivity Conference – bringing ~150 executives together in Barbados to discuss and solve strategic problems associated with corporate rebranding. [SVP; DHQ]</i></p>
CHQ	Communication	Sensitization	<p><i>Responsible for the entire communications strategy articulating “why the decision” was made to rebrand. Communication was critical to key stakeholders including, but not limited to, employees, customers, suppliers and shareholders. [CEO; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Video production – a common address by the Group CEO was distributed across the Group. [EVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Communication Plans – Developed by the CHQ’s Corporate Communications office and the Group CEO and the Business Unit Chairmen were “hands-on” in delivering key messages. [SVP; CHQ]</i></p>
CHQ	Socialization	Participation	<p><i>There was the Connectivity Conference held in Barbados bringing together key senior executives in Massy from across the region. [Director; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Special Events (e.g. Family Day in Trinidad, “Pan Pun de Sand” in Barbados) which brought together employees at the country level. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Organized a “Family Day” with all the companies in Trinidad to get “everybody on the same page” with the rebranding to Massy. [CEO; OHQ]</i></p>

Source: Author’s field notes and coding analysis

Interpretation

This initiative had a profound impact on the brand identity of Massy companies across all territories, and it was conceived and directed by the CHQ, hence the major level of involvement from that level as indicated by the first finding. It is also important to note that this initiative required participation from over 10,000 employees across more than 70 operating companies (Massy, 2014), so the involvement from the divisional and operating company levels was pivotal particularly regarding implementation.

On the second finding and relating specifically to mechanisms for enabling cross-unit collaboration, authority manifesting as decision making and intermediation both show up as being critical. Starting with the first one, I

should say that the final decision making for such a major initiative could have only occurred at the CHQ level of Massy because of internal approval requirements as well as the fact that the intellectual property (e.g. trademarks) of many of the subsidiaries are legally owned by the parent company. Despite that, the decision making process at the parent board and CHQ level was not done in isolation. It required collaboration with the Group CEO ensuring that members of his Executive Committee, which included both CHQ and DHQ level executives, were engaged and aligned with the rationale behind Corporate Rebranding.

Once the decision was made to proceed, the roll-out of the initiative required major intermediation from the DHQs to ensure that the requirements of the CHQ were met. In the financial year 2014 when Corporate Rebranding took place, Massy was organized around six business segments (Massy, 2014) each with its own DHQ with overall executive oversight from an EVP or SVP. There were also Country Managers with DHQ structures in selected territories (e.g. Barbados and Guyana) which had several companies across multiple business segments. These Business Unit and Country DHQs were critical in channeling and translating the requirements of the CHQ to the OHQs, to ensure that implementation was done in a manner that was relevant for the respective operating units by taking into consideration industry and market nuances.

For example, the financial services companies operating in the general insurance, money services and consumer finance sectors are highly regulated compared to other business segments. Therefore, it was important for the DHQ to highlight to the CHQ the regulatory approvals required (e.g. company name

changes) that may have resulted in longer gestation periods thereby impacting the overall project timeline. In the other direction on the vertical organizational dimension, the DHQs spent a lot of time engaging the OHQs explaining the rationale for the initiative to get those teams on board in alignment with the CHQ's expectations.

This form of intermediation was crucial, as the operating companies were giving up long-standing company brand identities which all their customers, suppliers and other key stakeholders became so betrothed to over decades, so it was understandably worrying for the teams that this level. Both the Business Unit and Country DHQs engaged with the OHQs under their purview, so depending on the territory, some operating companies received multiple engagement interactions with a common message albeit from different organizational actors, but this helped to reinforce alignment on Corporate Rebranding.

The third finding speaks to the use of communication manifesting as inclusion and sensitization, and socialization manifesting as participation. Firstly, inclusion was primarily about the arrangement of gatherings to involve key internal stakeholders at different levels in planning, and an interesting insight is that many of these gatherings were largely activated by either the CHQ or OHQ levels. The CHQ was focused on governing the strategy behind Corporate Rebranding ensuring that certain standards were met, but it also sought to involve other levels in the planning, so they organized key meetings to facilitate this. For example, there was a major event conceived by the CHQ called the Connectivity Conference which was held in Barbados bringing the company's

most senior executives together to align and develop plans for the implementation of Corporate Rebranding.

The OHQs were focused on implementation 'on the ground', so it was important for them to also get alignment within their respective companies. Therefore, as the initiative progressed, most of the OHQs held town hall meetings with the main purpose to engender support from the management and staff of the operating companies who ultimately were the ones needed to deliver the activities needed to make Corporate Rebranding a reality.

The CHQ played a major role in sensitization which occurred as reinforcing communicative activities once there was full alignment by all key internal stakeholders to proceed. These activities mostly came in the form of company-wide communication media such as emails, memos, and video messages from the Group CEO. There was also focused communication and messaging within divisions or business units, or territories tailor-made for those respective audiences.

Creating participatory social activities which completed the communication strategies described above, was also a major role played by the CHQ, and it was highly complementary to inclusion activities. Forums such as the Connectivity Conference did not only involve planning, but also social activities (e.g. evening dinners and cocktail parties) which helped to strengthen relationships between persons from different levels, countries and businesses who previously had limited opportunities to meet in person. Another example of a participation in a large social gathering was Family Day in Trinidad which was

planned by the CHQ. This involved all the employees and their families participating in an event to celebrate the launch of the new Massy brand in that market. Participating in events of this nature helped to foster collaboration, attain alignment and acceptance of the company's new brand identity.

Closing Remarks

The Corporate Rebranding case involved a strategic initiative to rebrand the corporate identities of more several subsidiaries operating in multiple businesses in different territories. The Corporate Rebranding initiative originated at the CHQ level where key decision making, and approvals were required. The utilization of Authority manifesting as intermediation particularly by the DHQ was critical given the required level of alignment across all three HQ organizational levels.

Communication and socialization were the two other integrative devices harnessed in this case. They manifested primarily as inclusive planning sessions and targeted communication strategies and as social participation in special forums respectively, all mainly triggered by the CHQ with DHQ support in coordination. Together, these devices were instrumental in enabling the level of cross-unit collaboration required to implement the project successfully.

At the end of financial year 2014, the Corporate Rebranding initiative was successfully completed:

“After the public launch in Trinidad and Tobago and Barbados on June 30 and July 1, 2014 respectively, we triggered a sequence of launches to the other territories in which we operate – Miami, Jamaica and Guyana were completed in 2014 and St. Lucia will be completed in 2015.”

Group CEO's Report (Massy, 2014)

Findings & Interpretation Within Case: Regional Procurement

Regional Procurement concerns aligning the business units within Massy to leverage economies of scale and scope, thereby reducing overall operating costs, by introducing a centralized approach to procuring indirect goods and services. Extracts from Massy's 2017 and 2018 Annual Reports provide additional insight:

“Further, executive management of the Group have embarked on a number of profit enhancing initiatives including, cost containment, procurement, shared services and continuous improvement initiatives. I am optimistic that these initiatives will help to reduce the operating costs of the Group and thereby make the Group more competitive.”

Chairman's Report (Massy, 2017)

“In the period under review, the Group invested in creating an Indirect Procurement function, to leverage the Group's purchasing power to negotiate better prices on indirect goods and services. The initiative also looked at consumption and demand for indirect products and services and implemented strategies aimed at increasing all efficiencies in procurement and use of indirect goods. Along with the Group's ongoing continuous improvement initiatives, these efforts helped improve the Group's operational efficiency.”

Letter from the Group CEO (Massy, 2018)

“In fact, these savings amounted to \$21 million in 2018 and even more is expected for 2019 and beyond. These, and many other initiatives, contributed to the Group's improved Operational Efficiency Performance in 2018 as follows:

Travel expenses, and consolidation and synergies in ocean logistics resulted in savings of \$3.4 million and \$2.1 million respectively. Focus on marketing efficiencies has resulted in greater use of digital media. Our development in digital marketing provided the opportunity for the Group to reduce its marketing spend on specific, low-impact media by \$5 million. Our improvements, for the year under review, included the consolidation of regional service providers, customer-focused content creation and growth of our social media platforms.”

Letter from the Group CFO (Massy, 2018)

Findings

For this case, there were 14 informants, five from the CHQ level, four from the DHQ level and five from the OHQ level. As you can see in Figure 4.11 below, there were a total of 89 integrative device codes based on the informants' responses, and with respect to HQ levels assigned to these codes, the CHQ, DHQ and OHQ represented 76.4%, 21.3% and 2.2% of the total respectively. Regarding the integrative devices identified, authority represented 41.6% of the total, communication - 23.6%, cross-unit structure - 22.5%, formalization - 9.0%, multi-skilling - 2.2% and collective incentives - 1.1%.

Figure 4.11: Data Matrix on Frequencies of Integrative Devices and HQ Integration Roles Coded for the Regional Procurement Case

HQ Level	Authority			Formalization		Communication			Cross-Unit Structure		Multi-Skilling	Collective Incentives	All Integrative Devices	% Contrib.
	Decision Making	Resource Allocation	Intermediation	Governance	Standardization	Inclusion	Translation	Sensitization	Vertical Coordination	Horizontal Coordination	Managerial Transfer	Performance Management		
CHQ	3	18	3	3	3	11	0	7	16	1	2	1	68	76.4%
DHQ	4	2	5	0	2	0	1	2	3	0	0	0	19	21.3%
OHQ	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2.2%
Total	37			8		21			20		2	1	89	
% Contrib.	41.6%			9.0%		23.6%			22.5%		2.2%	1.1%	100.0%	

Source: Author's analysis

Authority was elaborated into the HQ integration roles of *decision making*, *resource allocation* and *intermediation*, communication into *inclusion*, *translation*, and sensitization, cross-unit structure into *vertical coordination* and *horizontal coordination*, formalization into *governance* and *standardization*, multi-skilling into *managerial transfer* and collective incentives into *performance management*. The issue tree in Figure 4.12 provides a graphical representation

of how the integrative devices that manifested in this case have been elaborated into respective HQ integration roles.

Figure 4.12: Issue Tree - Regional Procurement

Source: Author's analysis

Based on the empirical observations and frequencies, I highlight three key findings from the Regional Procurement case. The first is that the CHQ had the most significant involvement in implementing this initiative compared to the other two HQ levels. The second finding is that the use of authority manifesting as *resource allocation* together with the use of cross-unit structure manifesting as *vertical coordination*, were critical integrative devices deployed to support cross-unit collaboration. The third finding is that the use of communication manifesting as *inclusion* and *sensitization*, were also major integrative devices

deployed to enable cross-unit collaboration and help bring alignment to all key internal stakeholders that were involved in the Regional Procurement project. Table 4.9 illustrates how the informants expressed their views focusing on the main integrative devices utilized and their respective HQ integration roles highlighted above.

Table 4.9: Selected Informant Responses for Interview Questions 3 and 4 - Main Integrative Devices Utilized in the Regional Procurement Case

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
CHQ	Authority	Resource Allocation	<p><i>Provided resources to support the project - “they brought in a resource - McKinsey” and set up a Group Indirect Procurement team. [EVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The CHQ was also responsible for introducing change management practices for supporting effective implementation. [General Manager; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Set up the structure and team to support the development and execution of the Indirect Procurement initiative. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Selected consultants (i.e. McKinsey) to evaluate the opportunities for cost efficiency and reduction. [CEO; OHQ]</i></p>
DHQ	Authority	Resource Allocation	<p><i>Provided human resources from the operating companies to join the Group Indirect Procurement team. [SVP; DHQ]</i></p>
CHQ	Cross-Unit Structure	Vertical Coordination	<p><i>A Group Procurement department was formed with executives assigned to specific categories (e.g. Logistics, Marketing, IT & Telecommunications, Fleet & Travel) to drive initiatives forward. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Each initiative was assigned an Initiative Sponsor to give executive leadership more ownership and to support change management. Initiative Sponsors were generally senior executives (e.g. SVPs) and Group Procurement team members would check-in with their respective sponsors to resolve issues. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The Steering Committee was a key mechanism which included key executives from both the CHQ and DHQ – meetings were held every 2-3 weeks – attendees included McKinsey consultants and the Category Leads on the project team. [Analyst; DHQ]</i></p>
DHQ	Cross-Unit Structure	Vertical Coordination	<p><i>Centralized and filtered all indirect equipment purchases through the DHQ (i.e. Regional Property Development department). [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The structure of the ITC Business Unit itself helped to facilitate cross-unit collaboration in the centralized procurement of computers, printers, etc. [CEO; OHQ]</i></p>
CHQ	Communication	Inclusion	<p><i>There was a meeting held to kick off the Procurement initiative which involved ~50 executives from different</i></p>

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
			<p><i>business units and external consultants. The meeting involved ideation and brainstorming on various spend categories. Over time, many smaller meetings were held to iterate on the initial brainstorming session. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Forums were held in various territories which brought together several key executives to develop, discuss and problem-solve on the main strategic issues associated with Indirect Procurement. [SVP; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Group Strategic Sourcing Managers collaborated within the communities by providing updates on what is going on in the various spend categories and they also promote the generation of new ideas by facilitating ideation sessions. [Group Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Roadshows to acknowledge the pain points caused by the method of initial roll-out and to engage the various stakeholders on how the process can be improved. [EVP; CHQ]</i></p>
CHQ	Communication	Sensitization	<p><i>Emails were sent by the Group Chief Procurement Officer to make everyone aware and provide updates on the initiative. [Shane; Managing Director; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Communicating across the enterprise that there is going to be a new function called Group Procurement and what the role and responsibilities will be. [Group Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Memos were sent via email across the Group from key executives (e.g. Group CEO) articulating “what we were doing and why we needed to do it”. [Analyst; DHQ]</i></p>
DHQ	Communication	Sensitization	<p><i>For example, in Retail, the SVP & Executive Chairman was responsible for communicating the details of the specific initiative to the various Massy Stores operating company CEOs across the region. This was an important part of the process of achieving “buy-in”. [Group Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The DHQ was not very involved in the Indirect Procurement exercise, apart from the SVP/Country Manager providing support for the vision and overall initiative. [Managing Director; OHQ]</i></p>

Source: Author’s field notes and coding analysis

Interpretation

Regional Procurement was another company-wide initiative that involved all three HQ organizational levels and impacted all business segments and territories which Massy operated in. Like Corporate Rebranding, Regional Procurement originated at the CHQ level, and the main objective was to reduce Massy’s overall operating costs by introducing global best practices in procurement, specifically for indirect goods and services, and implementing the

commensurate strategies. As such, the first finding indicating that the CHQ had the most significant involvement compared other HQ levels was not unexpected as it was organizational instigator. The DHQs and OHQs appeared to be more focused on execution activities based on the agreed course of direction set by the CHQ.

The second finding points to authority manifesting as resource allocation and cross-unit structure manifesting as vertical coordination together as critical for achieving the level of cross-unit collaboration required in the Regional Procurement initiative. As it relates to resource allocation, the CHQ was very active in that it put in place a dedicated Project Team, whose members were selected from different organizational levels, business segments and territories across the firm.

The people from this team were selected based on their successful track records in their own respective areas, comprehensive understanding of the entire company, as well as their strong internal network. These characteristics collectively were deemed to be essential to help make the initiative a success given the significant amount of buy-in, change management and collaboration that was needed. The CHQ also appointed the global management consulting firm, McKinsey & Company, to work with the Project Team and support this initiative given their substantial experience advising and directly steering procurement engagements for large firms globally.

During the earlier phases of the initiative, the Project Team reported into a Steering Committee which was comprised of the Group CEO, EVPs, and SVPs

with diverse responsibilities. The main role of the Steering Committee was to govern the overall initiative, by providing strategic direction to the Project Team, and to also ratify key decisions. Therefore, the Project Team, through the guidance given by the Steering Committee, acted as a structural device for vertical coordination across different HQ organizational levels.

The Project Team eventually evolved into a new CHQ department entitled Group Procurement, which was led by a Chief Procurement Officer reporting to the Group CFO. Five Strategic Sourcing Managers were appointed to report directly to the Chief Procurement Officer and there were also administrative associates hired to work in this new department to support the overall team. All leaders appointed to executive and management positions in this department were from the original Project Team, and notably the Strategic Sourcing Managers' responsibilities were divided between five main spend categories namely Technology, Logistics, Fleet & Travel, Marketing and Maintenance, Repairs & Operations.

In special circumstances, operating companies or business units were appointed by the CHQ to lead some procurement activities and by extension these entities played a vertical coordination role. For example, given its industry experience and vendor relationships with companies such as Hewlett Packard Enterprise, IBM, Dell EMC, and Oracle, Massy's Information Technology & Communications Business Unit was given the remit to coordinate the procurement of selected hardware and software solutions for the whole organization. Therefore, the CHQ's Group Procurement responsibilities were passed to this DHQ given its internal capabilities, which demonstrates how

resource allocation and vertical coordination across multiple HQ levels can be complementary.

As the third finding highlights, inclusion and sensitization were also important HQ integration role manifestations of communication. Inclusion chiefly came in the form of special meetings and roadshows which typically involved key internal stakeholders from all HQ levels. The purpose of these sessions was to get these stakeholders aligned to the strategic direction and enable greater participation in the idea generation, problem solving and planning for Regional Procurement.

An example of these special meetings is the ideation sessions facilitated by the Project Team and external consultants. These sessions brought personnel together from various HQ levels, businesses, and countries to brainstorm and identify opportunities for savings across the various spend categories.

Roadshows were also important as they involved the Group Procurement department travelling to different territories to directly engage the leadership of the businesses to strengthen relationships and collaboration to enhance the impact of the initiative.

These roadshows also acted as a form of sensitization to provide updates and general communication on what was happening with the initiative. Further communication via memos and emails by the Group CEO and Group Chief Procurement Officer helped to reinforce the importance and intentions of the project, as well as provide key updates on progress.

Closing Remarks

The Regional Procurement case involved an initiative to introduce global best practices in procurement across the Massy Group with the primary objective of enhancing efficiency and reducing operating costs. Regional Procurement was initiated at the CHQ, which was the most involved in key decision making and coordination compared to other HQ levels. The use of authority manifesting as resource allocation and cross-unit structure manifesting as vertical coordination were applied synergistically to promote cross-unit collaboration across multiple dimensions. Communication as an integrative device was also used, manifesting as both inclusion and sensitization, to assist with engagement via joint planning, and to help reinforce collective alignment on the direction of the initiative.

While the Regional Procurement initiative utilized a lot of company resources and it was of strategic importance in its heyday, the corporate strategy of Massy evolved thereafter to an operating model that granted greater autonomy to the business units, which lessened the appetite for 'federal' initiatives of this nature heralded by the CHQ. As such, the Group Procurement department was officially disbanded in 2019, albeit the knowledge, processes and systems introduced through the Regional Procurement initiative were still applied appropriately in the businesses based on their priorities. An extract from the 2019 Annual Report provides some additional strategic context on this pivot in strategy and the resultant impact to Regional Procurement:

“The Group invested significant time and resources into an internal diagnostic to assess inefficiencies and opportunities for improvement in manual back-office functions duplicated across the Group in Finance, Information Technology, Procurement and Human Resources. We assessed the opportunity for cost savings and improving the efficiency and effectiveness of our operations by either creating a Shared Services Centre to conduct these activities for all units in the Group or to outsource these activities

After extensive study, several specific opportunities were identified within Business Units and commonly across the Group. Having undertaken to set up the more autonomous industry portfolios, the opportunities for savings that were identified in the analysis will be pursued within each Portfolio and Line of Business.”

Letter from the Group CEO (Massy, 2019)

Findings & Interpretation Within Case: Group Policies

This case is about the ongoing activities associated with harmonizing policies across the Massy Group in several different functional areas such as HR, HSSE, IT and Legal. Extracts from the company’s Annual Reports show key examples of initiatives related to developing and implementing group-wide policies, procedures, and systems:

“We have also conducted on-going HSSE training to have in house HSSE professionals trained as US OSHA General Industry authorised trainers. These US OSHA General Industry authorised trainers will in turn train other Massy employees internally on various critical areas pertaining to HSSE. Additionally, this past year saw safety leadership training being facilitated for the Integrated Retail Business Unit in Barbados and Trinidad, and this was conducted to enhance the Massy Leadership’s commitment to HSSE, and contribute to a more seamless adoption and implementation of Corporate HSSE Policies and Procedures.”

Group CEO’s Report (Massy, 2015)

“This year, we charged ourselves with the task of transforming the leadership of the organisation by changing and clearly articulating the expectations of Massy leaders, across all businesses. The expectations are based on more service oriented, values-based leadership, which is recognised as essential to the sustained success of the Group. The roll-out of the new expectations of Massy leaders commenced with a number of workshops conducted by a diverse group of Senior Executives, who created a space for full understanding and appreciation of the responsibilities which are expected of all Massy leaders.”

Group CEO's Report (Massy, 2016)

"The Governance and Compensation Committee and the Board have supported the development/revision of certain key governance policy documents including; The Code of Conduct Ethics Policy, the Conflict of Interest Policy and the Speak Up Policy (formerly the Whistle-blower Policy). The Governance and Compensation Committee was also instrumental in the development of a Subsidiary Board Policy which will provide further guidance to subsidiary boards and enhance subsidiary governance across the Group."

Chairman's Report (Massy, 2017)

"Lastly, it gives me great pleasure to report that the Group's General Counsel, Ms. Angélique Parisot-Potter was promoted to the position of Executive Vice President (EVP), Business Integrity and Group General Counsel. This promotion comes in recognition of the value that Angélique brings to the Group in improving its internal legal services and in her initiative to develop and implement a Group-wide business integrity programme."

Letter from the Chairman (Massy, 2019)

Findings

For this case, there were 15 informants, six from the CHQ level, five from the DHQ level and four from the OHQ level. As Figure 4.13 illustrates, there were a total of 117 integrative device codes based on the informants' responses, and with respect to HQ levels assigned to these codes, the CHQ, DHQ and OHQ represented 65.0%, 29.1% and 6.0% of the total respectively. Regarding the integrative devices identified, Formalization represented 33.3% of the total, Communication - 29.1%, Authority - 26.5%, Cross-Unit Structure - 5.1%, Socialization - 5.1% and Collective Incentives - 0.9%.

Figure 4.13: Data Matrix on Frequencies of Integrative Devices and HQ Integration Roles Coded for the Group Policies Case

HQ Level	Authority			Formalization		Communication			Cross-Unit Structure	Socialization	Collective Incentives	All Integrative Devices	% Contrib.
	Decision Making	Resource Allocation	Intermediation	Governance	Standardization	Inclusion	Translation	Sensitization	Vertical Coordination	Participation	Performance Management		
CHQ	8	3	0	20	8	20	0	4	6	6	1	76	65.0%
DHQ	6	1	8	7	3	2	4	3	0	0	0	34	29.1%
OHQ	5	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	7	6.0%
Total	31			39		34			6	6	1	117	
% Contrib.	26.5%			33.3%		29.1%			5.1%	5.1%	0.9%	100.0%	

Source: Author's analysis

Formalization was elaborated into the HQ integration roles of *governance* and *standardization*, communication into *inclusion*, *translation* and *sensitization*, authority into *decision making*, *resource allocation* and *intermediation*, cross-unit structure into *vertical coordination*, socialization into *participation*, and collective incentives into *performance management*. The issue tree in Figure 4.14 provides a graphical representation of how the integrative devices that manifested in this case have been elaborated into respective HQ integration roles.

Figure 4.14: Issue Tree - Group Policies

Source: Author's analysis

Based on the empirical observations and frequencies, I highlight three key findings arising from the Group Policies case. The first finding is that the CHQ and DHQ together played the most significant roles with respect to involvement in conceiving and rolling out policies across the firm. The second finding is that the application of formalization manifesting as *governance* bundled with authority manifesting as *decision making* and *intermediation* were critical integrative devices utilized to support cross-unit collaboration.

The third finding is that the use of communication manifesting as *inclusion* was also a major device deployed to support cross-unit collaboration required to successfully establish the requisite policies across the Group. Table 4.10

illustrates how the informants expressed their views focusing on the main integrative devices utilized and their respective HQ integration roles highlighted above.

Table 4.10: Selected Informant Responses for Interview Questions 3 and 4 - Main Integrative Devices Utilized in the Group Policies Case

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
CHQ	Authority	Decision Making	<p><i>A good example is the Office365 initiative. The Group Chief Technology Officer (CTO) came up with idea and the CHQ mandated that it should be implemented across the Group with a specific deadline. [Supervisor; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Policies “are designed for all to follow” at the CHQ level. [Corporate Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The CHQ generally sets the tone. If not, “anarchy will reign”. This strategic initiative originated at the CHQ with the Group CEO mandating the harmonization of Group policies across all territories. [Manager; DHQ]</i></p>
DHQ	Authority	Decision Making	<p><i>Provide feedback to determine if the Group policies can work for their respective business unit / industry vertical. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The DHQ is the first point of contact for feedback before ratification of policies and procedures. [Manager; DHQ]</i></p>
OHQ	Authority	Decision Making	<p><i>They reach out to the CHQ for leadership and assistance as it relates to getting Group policies in place - “In the absence of that, they create their own policies for their own specific needs”. [Corporate Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Advise the CHQ and DHQ on policies developed that are specific to the business. Interpret and provide feedback to the CHQ on new and existing policies. [Manager; OHQ]</i></p>
DHQ	Authority	Intermediation	<p><i>Ensuring that the operating companies execute based on the policies “coming down” from the CHQ. [Supervisor; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Making sure that the operating companies within the division follow policies in accordance with CHQ requirements. [SVP; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The second role involves ensuring that the “drill down” (i.e. implementation) occurs inside all the operating companies that fall within the purview of the respective portfolio. [Divisional Manager; DHQ]</i></p>
CHQ	Formalization	Governance	<p><i>Set broad policies based on legislative and regulatory requirements – in alignment with international best practices and standards. [Corporate Executive; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Identify opportunities to create polices that enable the company to capture economies of scale (e.g. business travel – one executive could be on the same business trip staying at the Ritz-Carlton and the other could be staying “in a dump”). [Divisional Executive; DHQ]</i></p>

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
			<i>Shape and develop the policies. Oversee – which is more a compliance function. Keep abreast with international trends and best practices in order to adjust existing and develop new policies. [Manager; OHQ]</i>
DHQ	Formalization	Governance	<i>No role played at the Business Unit DHQ, but at the Barbados country level Group policies were developed. [Director; OHQ]</i> <i>However, the Energy & Industrial Gases Business Unit is very structured divisionally, and therefore, plays a major role in policy development and alignment. [Corporate Executive; CHQ]</i>
CHQ	Communication	Inclusion	<i>A Group IT Conference was held in 2013-14 to bring together IT personnel across the Group to share experiences, network with each other, discuss various aspects of polices and allow third party vendors to showcase their products and services that could be potentially beneficial to the Group. [Supervisor; DHQ]</i> <i>Regional HR meetings and conference calls are held periodically depending on what is going on. Every HR Head across the Group is invited to attend. [Manager; OHQ]</i> <i>The OneHR conference is the main mechanism for collaboration on Group policies. [Director; OHQ]</i> <i>Executive Committee Meetings are used as a mechanism for receiving and sharing information on Group policies to foster collaborative efforts. [SVP; CHQ]</i>
DHQ	Communication	Inclusion	<i>There are also monthly meetings held at the country level in Barbados bringing together HSSE representatives from various operating companies. [Manager; DHQ]</i>

Source: Author's field notes and coding analysis

Interpretation

I believe that it is logical to assume that a global, enterprise-wide policy agenda in a large multibusiness or multinational corporation with multiple organizational levels would be typically set or driven by the CHQ. While that turned out to be true in the context of Massy, the DHQs also had a significant role to play in this Group Policies case as highlighted in the first finding. The DHQs' involvement was surprising to me at first, particularly as it relates to decision making.

However, as I attained a greater contextual understanding from the field notes and internal discussions of how implementing company-wide policies occurred

with Massy, then the importance of the DHQ's role in decision making became clearer, which I will elaborate on further below.

On the second finding, formalization manifesting as governance was a key integrative role of the CHQ. The specific governance mechanisms primarily came in the form of policy development, assurance, and training. The first two are conventional and go together in that the CHQ creates policies for the entire organization to follow, and then it also ensures compliance with functional activities such as internal audit and enterprise risk management. Training and education sessions hosted by the CHQ were also done periodically as reinforcing activities to support compliance of Group Policies. It should be noted that the Business Unit DHQs also developed policies and required assurance particularly in areas which are highly industry specific.

An example of a DHQ being heavily involved in policy development was in the Energy & Industrial Gases Business Unit with respect to HSSE as the operating companies in this division had significantly greater risk exposure to this area. Another example is in the financial services segments, which also created several policies and procedures to ensure regulatory compliance, given that the risk of non-compliance resulted in hefty fines depending on the regulatory body.

Following from this, it is clear why the DHQ level also had a key role in decision making on policies as well as intermediation, as the DHQs needed to collaborate between the CHQ and OHQs to ensure the appropriate level of customization was deployed based on industry or territory relevance. In some cases, the country DHQs also intervened because if a CHQ level policy that

was issued conflicted with local legislation for example, then it would have to be addressed in a manner that satisfies both the parent company and market requirements. Policies were also developed at the subsidiary level as company specific nuances also had to be catered for in the implementation of Group Policies, so hence why decision making at this level also manifested which in turn resulted in problem-solving interactions between the OHQs and their respective DHQs, as well as directly with the CHQ.

The third finding on communication manifesting as inclusion was triggered primarily from the CHQ level. The specific mechanisms utilized were forums that brought together functional communities from various across the firm to collaborate on a myriad of priority topics. An example of this was the OneHR Conference which was typically scheduled on an annual basis, and it was organized by the Group Senior Vice President of People & Culture and her Group HR team at the CHQ level. The OneHR Conference brought together all the HR leaders in Massy to one location for the purpose of discussing functional priorities and other topical agenda items such as Group Policies that impacted all operating entities.

These sessions also involved strategic planning and social activities that enabled collaboration between participants from different HQ levels, companies and countries who would not normally get the chance to do so in their typical day-to-day experiences. Other functional departments such as IT, HSSE, Legal and Finance hosted similar forums in person or virtually with a view to attaining alignment on key functional strategic areas including Group Policies.

Closing Remarks

Unlike the other cases, Group Policies is not a project, but more akin to continuous efforts to standardize policies across the company with mixed results depending on the function. The CHQ and DHQ both played most important roles in deploying integrative devices to achieve cross-unit collaboration. With respect to the devices applied, formalization manifesting as governance, authority manifesting as decision making and intermediation, along with communication manifesting as inclusion were together heavily utilized in the Group Policies case.

Findings & Interpretation Across Cases

Before delving straight into the narrative for the findings and interpretation across the cases, I thought that it would be useful to summarize key insights from the within case analyses which are represented in Figures 4.15 and 4.16.

Figure 4.15: Issue Tree - Integrative Devices & HQ Integration Roles, All

Cases

Source: Author's analysis

Figure 4.16: Major Integrative Devices Identified in Key Findings Across All

Cases

	Authority	Formalization	Communication	Cross-Unit Structure	Socialization	Multi-skilling	Collective Incentives
Guyana Retail Entry	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
Own Brands	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Corporate Rebranding	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
Regional Procurement	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Group Policies	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗

✓ Identified in the key findings as a major integrative device within the case
 ✗ Not identified as a major integrative device within the case

Source: Author's analysis

Findings

There are five salient findings that I highlight across the cases which are: 1) the HQ level of origination for the respective initiatives consistently takes on the most active role in deploying integrative devices, 2) the use authority in some form is a basic required integrative device to support cross-unit collaboration, 3) the utilization of communication manifesting as inclusion is critical for cross-unit collaboration to occur, 4) cross-unit structure manifesting as vertical coordination at the HQ level of origination is highly utilized primarily through structural operating mechanisms to support cross-unit collaboration and 5)

multi-skilling and collective incentives are the most taken for granted integrative devices given the common utilization of associated operating mechanisms in the case study organization.

Interpretation

From the data presented in Figure 4.4, the CHQ and DHQ were clearly the most involved HQ levels across all cases together representing 91.7% of the integrative device codes from the informants' responses. For the Guyana Retail Entry and Own Brands cases, the DHQ level was the most active, and for the other three cases Corporate Rebranding, Regional Procurement and Group Policies, the CHQ was the main driver. As indicated earlier, these HQ levels were also the originators of the respective initiatives and hence the articulation of the first finding.

My interpretation of this finding is that these origination HQ levels identified various opportunities for value creation across units and they may have presumed that greater involvement on their part would help to steer the initiatives along the critical paths to increase the likelihood of success. Of course, we know that success is not guaranteed given the outcome of initiatives such as the Own Brands and Regional Procurement which did not progress as anticipated by the DHQ and CHQ respectively relative to the original intentions. Conversely, the successful implementation of Corporate Rebranding and Guyana Retail Entry paints a different picture given the success of these projects, and Group Policies is an ongoing initiative with mixed results depending on the functional area.

In the second finding, I consider authority to be the basic required integrative device that Massy deploys to support cross-unit collaboration. From the data matrix in Figure 4.4, authority featured the most prominently representing 35.4% of the integrative device codes across all cases. Moreover, authority materialized in the key findings as a major integrative device across all five cases as you can see in Figure 4.16. Comparatively, communication came in at second place identified as a major integrative device in the key findings for four of the five cases, cross-unit structure for two cases, socialization, and formalization each in one case, while multi-skilling and collective incentives were not recognized at all in any of the key findings.

The consistent use of authority as a main integrative device in the key findings also resulted in a significant presence of two of its corresponding HQ integration roles across the cases. In this study, there are five cases and three HQ levels therefore resulting in a maximum of 15 touch points for integrative device code data to appear in. As Figure 4.4 illustrates, the top two ranking HQ integration roles which had the greatest coverage across all cases and HQ levels with 10 or more touch points were decision making (14) and resource allocation (10), both manifestations of authority.

Starting with decision making, perhaps it is natural to consider this as an everyday activity within organizations. However, decision making specifically in relation to the role HQ plays in supporting cross-unit collaboration in this study typically came through mandate complemented by referral and feedback.

Mandating involves the classic use of authority due to embedded organizational power structures (Castañer & Ketokivi, 2018) with a superior level emphasizing

the requirement to collaborate amongst units to achieve a desired objective. Referral and feedback are collectively characterized by continuous interactions, including but not limited to negotiation and consensus building, between multiple HQ levels to ensure there is clear alignment on what needs to be done collaboratively or otherwise to achieve the desired objective.

The issuance of mandates together with referral and feedback for decision making was evident across most of the cases as you would have seen in some of the above representative informant transcriptions. My interpretation of why these two seem to work together from the perspective of decision making is that, due to the heterogeneity of Massy, both by industry and geographically, there is an inherent need for customization when implementing initiatives driven by higher HQ levels to ensure relevance and sensible application to lower level units. Even in the Group Policies case, which by its name alone could be perceived as highly top-down in nature, there were edicts in the pursuit of enterprise-wide standardization, but tailoring was still frequently done at the unit levels (see Table 4.10).

As it relates to resource allocation, it shows up mainly in the form of leveraging internal capabilities. In the traditional sense, resource allocation via this mechanism is typically utilized as a managerial tool however, in the context of this study and across the cases, they were also utilized to support cross-unit collaboration and mostly activated by the origination HQ level. In several of the cases, key personnel were assigned to participate in project teams based on capabilities they developed in other relevant contextual circumstances within

Massy (e.g. the appointment of the Project Champion in Guyana Retail Entry and Regional Commercial Director in Own Brands).

My interpretation of why resource allocation regularly occurred in this manner is that the origination HQ level, by virtue of hierarchical position and viewpoint across different units in their domains, had the ability to identify internal resources with the aptitudes for cross-unit collaboration considered important to make the respect initiatives successful. Therefore, they selected personnel with these aptitudes, appointed them to key positions and gave them the requisite authority and overall responsibility with the assumption that this would increase the likelihood of success in execution. It is also worth mentioning that the appointment of suitable external consultants was also done in many cases (e.g. Regional Procurement, Corporate Rebranding and Own Brands) to augment the capabilities of the internal resources being leveraged.

Communication was identified in the key findings for four of the five cases as a major integrative device (see Figure 4.16), and its manifestation in the HQ integration role of inclusion was critical in ensuring that cross-unit collaboration occurs. The operating mechanisms attached to inclusion were typically in the form of gatherings (e.g. special meetings, seminars, conferences, town halls) of key internal stakeholders with the intention to align on a particular strategic matter.

Like the point I made above on decision making and resource allocation as manifestations of authority in the second finding, communication is customarily used as a managerial tool in business and naturally in language as part of our

daily lives. However in this study, I focus on communication specifically as an *integrative device*, aimed at instilling awareness and creating alignment on initiatives that may require organizational subunits to work together. Therefore, I interpret the consistent use of these inclusion gatherings across the cases by various HQ levels not only communicative in the general sense, but also to get subunits involved in strategic and other planning activities which can be helpful in supporting cross-unit collaboration to achieve a collective objective (Ketokivi & Castañer, 2004).

As Figure 4.4 illustrates, the top three integrative devices measured by contribution to the total number of integrative device codes are authority (35.4%), communication (28.8%) and formalization (14.4%). While cross-unit structure (13.6%) ranks in fourth place, it has a unique characteristic relative to the top three in that its HQ integration role manifestation of vertical coordination has the highest contribution (90.7%) within a single integrative device for the total across all cases. Vertical coordination was dominant not only in total across the cases, but also individually for each HQ level - CHQ (55.6%), DHQ (25.9%), OHQ (9.3%) - relative to the other HQ integration roles for the top three integrative devices.

This data insight led to the third key finding on the use of vertical coordination as a role played, particularly by the HQ level of origination, which involves the application of different types of structural operating mechanisms. As defined earlier, vertical coordination is about organizing people or teams across multiple HQ levels to achieve a desired objective. For the five cases being studied, there were a plethora of structural operating mechanisms utilized via vertical

coordination and they were either temporary or permanent in nature depending on the context of the initiative. My interpretation of why these mechanisms materialized so frequently is that they acted as boundary spanners (Goold & Campbell, 2002a) which promoted and influenced cross-unit collaboration across different HQ levels and other organizational dimensions once it was deemed critical in achieving the desired goals.

Two good examples of temporary structural operating mechanisms used across several of the cases were Steering Committees and Project Teams. These temporary mechanisms were put in place to support governance and performance management in the case of Steering Committees, and implementation with respect to the Project Teams. It is important to note that Steering Committees and Project Teams were often composed of members from different HQ levels, businesses, and territories inherently further fostering the desired level of cross-unit collaboration.

In connection with permanent structural operating mechanisms, there were two types utilized which can be classified as either new or existing structures. New structures were related to the creation of a new unit (e.g. Group Procurement department at the CHQ in Regional Procurement) which were assigned the authority at the origination HQ level for responsibilities which required collaboration between units which would not naturally occur. Existing structures were given similar remits, not necessarily at the origination HQ level, because they already had the capabilities and experience (e.g. Information Technology & Communications Business Unit in Regional Procurement) to immediately take on oversight responsibilities of a specific area.

The fourth finding suggests that collective incentives and multi-skilling were perhaps overlooked by the informants. These two devices together accounted for only five integrative device codes, or 1.3% of the total 396, derived from four informants across three cases, and attached to the CHQ level in each instance (see data matrix above in Figure 4.4). This scant number for these two devices was surprising for me, given my understanding as an insider of what transpires within Massy.

For example and as it relates to collective incentives, the use of balanced scorecards (Kaplan & Norton, 1992) as a performance management tool is utilized for all executive and senior management level personnel for their short term incentive plans which is a material part of their overall annual compensation. It is quite common for components of these scorecards to have line items that encourage cross-unit collaborative behaviors to achieve a desired objective, and the two coded responses included in Table 4.11 signifies this.

The situation with multi-skilling is akin to collective incentives in that although its use is pervasive in Massy, it does not receive much acknowledgement from many informants. A common usage I can think of is the transfer or secondment of personnel to support strategic initiatives based on their specialist or generalist experience and knowledge. This was very much evident in several of the cases including Corporate Rebranding, Regional Procurement, Own Brands and Guyana Retail Entry, where key personnel were assigned permanently in a new role or temporarily on a full-time basis to work on a project team. Table

4.11 also includes the three coded responses associated with Multi-skilling across all the cases that it appeared in due to the output of the coding process.

My general interpretation of the low recognition of these two integrative devices, is that the application of tools such as balanced scorecards, and the utilization of practices like managerial transfer or secondment have become highly institutionalized within the organizational context of Massy. These normative practices oftentimes result in personnel overlooking the existence of these same practices as articulated in notable contributions on institutional theory (Meyer & Rowan, 1977; DiMaggio & Powell, 1983).

Table 4.11: Selected Responses for Interview Questions 3 and 4 - Collective Incentives and Multi-skilling Across Cases

HQ Level	Integrative Device	HQ Integrat. Role	Representative Informant Transcriptions and/or Quotes
CHQ	Collective Incentives	Performance Management	<p><i>More recently, the Group Procurement team members were assigned balanced scorecards which hinge on achieving savings targets and promoting collaboration across the entire Group. [Manager; CHQ]</i></p> <p><i>Balanced Scorecards - the key components of the scorecards (i.e. Customer, Financial, Strategic, Business Improvement) inherently promote and facilitate cross-unit collaboration. [SVP; CHQ]</i></p>
CHQ	Multi-skilling	Managerial Transfer	<p><i>The selection of Group Strategic Sourcing Managers from key positions across the Massy Group that had a good understanding of the respective Business Unit and Country cultures, as well as subject areas, which helped to facilitate greater collaboration [CEO; OHQ]</i></p> <p><i>There was diverse set of persons from different functions, business units and countries assigned to support the roll-out of the Corporate Rebranding initiative. [Manager; DHQ]</i></p> <p><i>The diversification of the team members selected to join the Group Indirect Procurement department supported cross-unit collaborative thinking as they came from various businesses across different territories. [General Manager; OHQ]</i></p>

Source: Author's field notes and coding analysis

Closing Remarks

The key findings and their associated interpretations across the cases were highlighted based on differences and similarities that stood out to and ultimately helped to frame my responses to the research questions. This along with the findings within the cases will form the basis of my conclusions and ultimate research contributions which are articulated next in Chapter Five.

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

Introduction

The purpose of this multiple case study was to explore with a sample of informants, that participated in various initiatives within a large firm, to attain their perspectives on the role that multiple HQ levels play in cross-unit collaboration, as well as to understand how these respective HQ levels utilized integrative devices to support such cross-unit collaboration. Therefore, I asked these two research questions:

1. What is the role of multiple HQ levels in supporting cross-unit collaboration?
2. How do multiple HQ levels deploy integrative devices to support cross-unit collaboration?

My conclusions from this study aim to answer these research questions and follow from the findings and interpretations articulated in Chapter Four. More specifically, these conclusions arose from the key findings across the cases that I deemed to be the most significant to make a contribution with respect to the elaboration of existing organization theories.

Hence, I conclude that: 1) Both management and oversight are roles played at multiple HQ levels to enable cross-unit collaboration, 2) the use of authority manifesting as the HQ roles of decision making and resource allocation are *essential* for supporting cross-unit collaboration, and 3) the use of communication and cross-unit structure manifesting as the HQ roles of inclusion

and vertical coordination respectively are *critical* for supporting cross-unit collaboration. It should be noted that the first conclusion is meant to be a response to the first research question, while the second and third conclusions are meant to be responses to the second research question. On the latter two conclusions, I focused my attention only on authority, communication and cross-unit structure as from my perspective, they yielded the most interesting insights that offered a path to elaborating on their theoretical foundations as integrative devices.

As it relates to the structure of the chapter, the next sections include a discussion on the main findings and conclusions drawn, then I end with my perspectives on directions for future research taking into consideration some of the limitations associated with this study.

Cross-Unit Collaboration: Management and Oversight Occurs at all HQ Levels

As per the case sampling logic described in Chapter Three, I selected cases based on initiatives that originated from different HQ levels which for this study happens to be the CHQ and DHQ. The first key finding across the cases was that the HQ levels from which the initiatives originated were generally the most involved regarding the deployment of integrative devices to support cross-unit collaboration. Furthermore, the interpretation behind this finding was that the origination HQ levels may have assumed that greater involvement by them would have helped to keep the initiative along the path to achieving the desired objective.

As part of my conclusion associated with this finding, I am leveraging the recent perspectives of Ketokivi & Mahoney (2023) on the distinction between management and oversight from their Efficiency Lens framework. They indicate that management is about planning and coordination activities that can create value, while oversight comes in the form of ensuring that management teams act in the best interest of the overall organization. While I agree with this perspective which arose from the foundations of agency theory (Fama, 1980), the notion of top management teams or HQ-level resources doing managerial work alone, and a board of directors independently providing oversight of the same management teams takes for granted the reality of what occurs in a contemporary large firm that has multiple HQ and organizational levels (Menz, Kunisch & Collis, 2015).

As you can see from the cases examined within Massy, involvement by the various HQ levels was exhibited through both management and oversight. For example, project teams were often put in place by the CHQ (e.g. Regional Procurement and Corporate Rebranding) and DHQs (e.g. Guyana Retail Entry) as to support planning and coordination. Additionally, these same origination HQ levels also established committees (e.g. Steering Committee) to provide oversight of the same project teams for governance and performance management. In both instances, it was the management teams of the different HQ levels providing both management and oversight roles to achieve the respective objectives.

Within the context of Massy, the CHQ and DHQ levels both performed roles primarily related to originating initiatives, then mobilizing resources and

establishing infrastructure for execution, as well as providing communication forums to ensure alignment. Based on the data collected and analyzed in the study, the OHQ did not play a material role in these areas, but as expected, this level was more focused on implementation. Therefore, the general essence of my conclusion is that the role of HQ at different levels involves both management and oversight with respect to the deployment of integrative devices to support cross-unit collaboration.

How Authority Manifests as an Essential Integrative Device

When authority manifests through the HQ role of decision making in this organizational context, there appears to be a consistent balance between the HQ level of origination issuing a mandate of some form, while subsequently engaging in continuous feedback with the other levels to come to a mutually agreed position. This manifestation aligns similarly to Chester Barnard's perspective (Mahoney, 2002) highlighted almost a century ago, which suggests that the notion of authority effectively occurs less through command and control, but more through *persuasion* and *negotiations* between different organizational levels.

When authority manifests via the HQ role of resource allocation, it is primarily about appointing key personnel for executive oversight and accountability, or in the form of leveraging internal resources for their experiences or capabilities deemed to be relevant for the initiative including the support for cross-unit collaboration.

Based on the findings across the cases, I conclude that authority is an essential integrative device, meaning that its application is a necessary condition for cross-unit collaboration. I draw this conclusion because in a company like Massy where many of the business units and their respective subsidiaries are not as related to others, then the need increases for intervening roles to organize with a view to capturing value from initiatives involving cross-unit collaboration. Therefore, the use of authority to activate such initiatives via decision making in a manner involving engagement and persuasion, as well as ensuring the appropriate resources are appropriately allocated for implementation, seems like logical essential roles for particularly the origination HQ levels to play.

How Communication Manifests as a Critical Integrative Device

Based on the findings across the cases, I conclude that communication is a critical integrative device, meaning that it is not absolutely required, but is still extremely important for cross-unit collaboration to occur. When communication manifests through the HQ role of inclusion, it typically comes in the form of bringing people together from different units in various forums to ensure that there is a clear understanding of what an initiative is all about and enhances overall alignment. This reconciles with Ketokivi & Castañer's (2004) perspective that participation and involvement in such collaborative activities promotes organizational convergence.

I draw this conclusion because in the case study organizational context, the use of communication for the purpose of integration can be helpful in enacting cross-unit collaboration given that the units do not seem to voluntarily come

together for initiatives that require such collaboration. I recognize that in other organizational environments, units may organically collaborate as Martin & Eisenhardt's (2010) concept of 'rewiring' suggests, but this is not the case in firm contexts like Massy with a portfolio encompassing units, in which many are not closely related by industry or other characteristics.

How Cross-Unit Structure is used as a Critical Integrative Device

When cross-unit structure manifests through the HQ role of vertical coordination, it arises in the form of putting in place permanent (e.g. new departments) or temporary structures (e.g. project teams, steering committees) for both management and oversight of an initiative thereby promoting any requirements for cross-unit collaboration. Earlier, I defined vertical coordination as the process of organizing people and teams across multiple HQs on different organizational levels, and horizontal coordination as the process of organizing people and teams across multiple HQs on the same organizational level.

These definitions are important as they inherently point to the reality of integration occurring 'across' organizational boundaries and not traditionally 'within' an organization. As typified in extant insights on cross-unit structure, there seems to be a significant focus on the deployment of lateral structures to facilitate integration happening within firms across functional areas (e.g. Finance, Operations, Product Development). However, in firms such as Massy, cross-unit collaboration also occurs between units in different territories and business segments, as well as HQ levels, and these units are generally separate legal entities. Following from this, I draw the conclusion of cross-unit structure being critical since the structures mentioned above are highly

complementary to the use of authority in mobilizing teams across businesses, territories, or HQ levels to support implementation and they also provide reinforcement for effective communication through inclusive activities.

Directions for Future Research

To set the stage for the discussion on opportunities for future research, I believe it is important for me to concurrently acknowledge the limitations associated with the characteristics of this study. Firstly, the boundary conditions in respect to the research setting is an inherent limitation simply because I conducted this study in one firm. Furthermore, even though I selected multiple cases, the findings derived from this study may not be transferable to other organizational contexts. This presents an opportunity to replicate this kind of case study research in other contexts taking into consideration variations in company size, level of industry, business or product diversification, geographic reach, ownership (public vs privately owned) and even organizational culture.

In Chapter Four, I included a section that provided additional context on the general role of HQ within Massy. The key finding on this matter was that at the time the study was being conducted, the company was evolving from a management and oversight operating model that was more centralized to one that can be classified as decentralization with coordinated control (Garvin & Levesque, 2006). Thus, I believe that there is a significant opportunity to specifically further our understanding on the role that multiple HQs play in cross-unit collaboration and integration in general, by studying firms with different parenting styles (Goold, Campbell & Alexander, 1994). By extension, I

am sure that we can improve our understanding of how integrative devices are deployed in these different organizational circumstances.

Secondly, another area to highlight is my sampling logic for the cases. I purposely selected cases which originated at the CHQ and DHQ to ensure coverage of multiple HQ levels in initiatives that involved cross-unit collaboration. This sampling logic may imply to some readers that initiatives that are deemed to be strategic or important primarily originate at higher organizational levels in a top-down manner compared to a bottom-up approach (Mintzberg, 1978; Beer & Nohria, 2000), which is not necessarily the case across the board. Therefore, it would be interesting to understand how the findings would materialize with cases that comprise initiatives that originate at the OHQ level or even deeper within operating companies.

Lastly, as an executive within Massy (i.e. an insider) who personally conducted all the interviews, it is reasonable to assume the existence of informant response bias (Yin, 2014). Additionally, as a long-standing employee of the firm and very familiar with the case study organization, I may have preconceived notions that could have affected my objectivity resulting in some form of researcher bias (Nosek, Spies & Motyl, 2012). Hence, there is an opportunity for this study to be replicated in the same or other organizations being led by a non-insider to see if similar or contrasting results are yielded.

Final Reflections

My experience as a part-time doctoral researcher has been challenging but also quite rewarding in the eight years since I officially enrolled in the doctoral

program at IE Business School. Admittedly, it was very taxing both personally and professionally to be focusing on building my career from being an Analyst back then to now a Senior Vice President, while simultaneously taking on this doctoral research project. However, even if I could go back in time, I would not change the way it all evolved as it was an enriching experience conducting research within an organization that I spent almost half my entire lifetime based on my age at the time of writing!

I provided some self-reflections earlier in Chapter Three that referred to my experience as an insider researcher. While there may be shortcomings related to being an insider while conducting case study research, there are also huge benefits, like having greater organizational context within the firm and having access to sensitive internal company information that would be otherwise difficult to attain. In addition to this, I would like to highlight the partnership with my doctoral advisor, which was instrumental in getting me to the finish line by guiding me through the entire process, making my research better positioned for examination by an academic audience.

I personally believe that there is a tremendous opportunity to enhance our overall knowledge of how organizations function by creating greater synergies between 'practitioner insiders with an affinity for organizational research', and 'professional academics with an affinity for research inside organizations'. We need more partnerships in this regard to ensure the appropriate balance between rigor and relevance in our continual pursuit of new scholarly insight.

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APPENDIX A: ADDITIONAL MASSY COMPANY PROFILE INFORMATION

Figure A1: Massy's Geographical Footprint as of September 30th, 2019

Source: Massy (2019)

Figure A2: Massy's Revenue Split by Territory and Business Unit, FY 2019

A&IE: Automotive & Industrial Equipment
 E&IG: Energy & Industrial Gases
 IR: Integrated Retail Business Unit
 ITC: Information Technology & Communications
 FS: Financial Services Line of Business
 Other: Other Investments

Source: Massy (2019)

APPENDIX B: DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

Figure B1: Example of Email Invitation and Informant Confirmation Response

Jeremy Nurse

From: [REDACTED]
Sent: Tuesday, January 22, 2019 10:26 AM
To: Jeremy Nurse
Subject: RE: Interview with [REDACTED] - Jeremy Nurse's Doctoral Research

Good day Jeremy,

Yes I will meet you for the interview on Saturday, January 26th at 10 a.m., at a location convenient to you in Barbados to discuss the topic of Corporate Rebranding for the Massy Group, for purposes of your doctoral research.

[REDACTED]
 Group Strategic Sourcing Manager - Marketing

63 Park Street
 Port-of-Spain, Trinidad, W.I
 T 1 868 625 3426 ext 2121

[REDACTED]
www.massygroup.com

From: Jeremy Nurse
Sent: Tuesday, January 22, 2019 8:24:19 AM
To: [REDACTED]
Subject: Interview with [REDACTED] - Jeremy Nurse's Doctoral Research

Dear [REDACTED]

I am writing to find out if it would be possible for me to interview you for the purpose of my doctoral research.

My research involves an empirical investigation into the role of corporate headquarters in cross-unit collaboration and I would like to engage you in a brief discussion on **Corporate Rebranding**. It should be noted that no preparation is required for the interview and it should take approximately 60 minutes.

Please let me know if you are willing to participate and if so, I will reach out to you in a separate correspondence or via call to confirm your availability to meet.

Thank you kindly in advance.

Regards,

Jeremy M. Nurse
 Director, Strategy & Business Development

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Source: Author's corporate email with redactions

Table B1: Additional Details on Key Informants by Case

#	Case	Official Title of Key Informant	HQ Level	Date Completed	Duration (h:mm)
1	Group Policies	Group SVP - Legal & Group General Counsel	Corporate: CHQ	05-Apr-2019	1:07
2	Group Policies	General Manager (Previously Group Chief Technology Officer)	Corporate: CHQ	05-Jan-2019	2:01
3	Group Policies	Group Health, Safety, Security & Environment Director	Corporate: CHQ	04-Jun-2019	1:23
4	Group Policies	Lead Counsel	Corporate: CHQ	09-May-2019	1:04
5	Group Policies	Information Systems Security Manager	Corporate: CHQ	17-Dec-2018	1:26
6	Group Policies	Group Risk Manager	Corporate: CHQ	07-May-2019	1:14
7	Group Policies	Head of Human Resources	Divisional: DHQ	17-Dec-2018	1:35
8	Group Policies	Director - Labour Relations	Divisional: DHQ	04-Jan-2019	1:16
9	Group Policies	Manager - Health, Safety & Environment	Divisional: DHQ	18-Dec-2018	1:45
10	Group Policies	Group Technology Services Unit Supervisor	Divisional: DHQ	20-Dec-2018	1:15
11	Group Policies	Infrastructure Administrator	Divisional: DHQ	04-Jan-2019	1:27
12	Group Policies	Human Resources Director	Operating Company: OHQ	02-May-2019	1:17
13	Group Policies	Human Resources Manager	Operating Company: OHQ	18-Feb-2019	1:28
14	Group Policies	Legal Officer	Operating Company: OHQ	26-Apr-2019	1:01
15	Group Policies	IT Administrator	Operating Company: OHQ	04-Mar-2019	1:23
16	Regional Procurement	Group EVP & Chief Financial Officer	Corporate: CHQ	03-Jun-2019	1:17
17	Regional Procurement	Group Chief Procurement Officer	Corporate: CHQ	11-Jan-2019	0:55
18	Regional Procurement	Group Strategic Sourcing Manager - Logistics	Corporate: CHQ	07-Jan-2019	1:15
19	Regional Procurement	Group Strategic Sourcing Manager - IT, Telecoms & HR	Corporate: CHQ	11-Jan-2019	1:28
20	Regional Procurement	Group Strategic Sourcing Manager - Fleet & Travel	Corporate: CHQ	07-May-2019	1:10
21	Regional Procurement	Group EVP & Executive Chairman - Integrated Retail	Divisional: DHQ	09-May-2019	1:15
22	Regional Procurement	Group SVP & Executive Chairman - IT & Communications	Divisional: DHQ	05-Apr-2019	1:19
23	Regional Procurement	Regional Property Development Director	Divisional: DHQ	19-Feb-2019	1:27
24	Regional Procurement	Business Analyst	Divisional: DHQ	07-Feb-2019	1:28
25	Regional Procurement	Chief Executive Officer	Operating Company: OHQ	06-May-2019	1:09
26	Regional Procurement	Chief Executive Officer	Operating Company: OHQ	26-Feb-2019	2:05
27	Regional Procurement	Managing Director	Operating Company: OHQ	06-Mar-2019	0:55
28	Regional Procurement	Managing Director	Operating Company: OHQ	21-Feb-2019	1:25
29	Regional Procurement	General Manager	Operating Company: OHQ	26-Apr-2019	1:10
30	Corporate Rebranding	President & Group CEO	Corporate: CHQ	03-Jun-2019	0:52
31	Corporate Rebranding	Group SVP - Corporate Governance & Corporate Secretary	Corporate: CHQ	10-May-2019	1:21
32	Corporate Rebranding	Manager - Corporate Branding & Communications	Corporate: CHQ	15-Mar-2019	2:00
33	Corporate Rebranding	Group Strategic Sourcing Manager - Marketing	Corporate: CHQ	26-Jan-2019	2:01
34	Corporate Rebranding	Group EVP & Executive Chairman - Integrated Retail (Retired)	Divisional: DHQ	10-Feb-2019	2:24
35	Corporate Rebranding	Group EVP & Executive Chairman - Automotive	Divisional: DHQ	09-May-2019	1:29
36	Corporate Rebranding	Group SVP & Executive Chairman - Financial Services	Divisional: DHQ	19-Feb-2019	1:15
37	Corporate Rebranding	Chief Administrative Officer - Barbados (Retired)	Divisional: DHQ	17-Apr-2019	3:14
38	Corporate Rebranding	Public Relations Manager	Divisional: DHQ	01-Apr-2019	1:45
39	Corporate Rebranding	Chief Executive Officer	Operating Company: OHQ	06-May-2019	1:50
40	Corporate Rebranding	Director, Business Development, Strategy & Marketing	Operating Company: OHQ	19-Jun-2019	2:36
41	Corporate Rebranding	Operations Director	Operating Company: OHQ	06-Apr-2019	1:05
42	Corporate Rebranding	General Manager	Operating Company: OHQ	14-Feb-2019	1:21
43	Corporate Rebranding	Art Director / IT Manager	Operating Company: OHQ	01-Feb-2019	1:00
44	Corporate Rebranding	Marketing Manager	Operating Company: OHQ	08-May-2019	1:38
45	Own Brands	Group SVP & Executive Chairman - Other Investments	Divisional: DHQ	17-Mar-2019	1:32
46	Own Brands	Regional Commercial Director	Divisional: DHQ	21-Feb-2019	1:33
47	Own Brands	Business Development Analyst	Divisional: DHQ	08-Feb-2019	1:26
48	Own Brands	Managing Director	Operating Company: OHQ	07-May-2019	0:50
49	Own Brands	Managing Director	Operating Company: OHQ	08-Apr-2019	1:09
50	Own Brands	Procurement Director	Operating Company: OHQ	06-Apr-2019	1:12
51	Own Brands	Buying Manager	Operating Company: OHQ	16-Apr-2019	1:06
52	Guyana Retail Entry	Group SVP & Executive Chairman - Retail	Divisional: DHQ	10-May-2019	1:00
53	Guyana Retail Entry	Regional Business Excellence Director	Divisional: DHQ	11-Mar-2019	1:50
54	Guyana Retail Entry	IT Director	Operating Company: OHQ	09-May-2019	3:02
55	Guyana Retail Entry	Human Resources Director	Operating Company: OHQ	08-May-2019	1:17
Total					80:48

Source: Compiled by author

APPENDIX C: PROFILE OF AUTHOR

Figure C1: Professional Bio of Jeremy M. Nurse as at April 20th, 2023

	<p>Mr. Jeremy Nurse is a senior executive and corporate strategist with over 19 years combined experience in business operations, strategy, corporate development and board membership across several industries including retail, distribution, manufacturing, logistics, consumer finance, energy, automotive and real estate.</p> <p>He is currently the Group Senior Vice President of Corporate Strategy & Transactions for the <u>Massy Group of Companies</u>. His key responsibilities involve leading teams in strategy development, business planning, new business and corporate development, as well as deal execution for M&A and divestiture transactions.</p> <p>Jeremy has a proven track record as a dealmaker having led various transaction teams in divesting over US\$270M equivalent in non-core assets throughout his career within the Massy Group.</p>
<p>Background</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Bachelor of Science (BSc), Mathematics with Physics (1st Class Honors), University of the West Indies, Cave Hill Campus, Barbados (2003). ▪ Master of Business Administration, Durham University, UK (2009). ▪ Master in Research Methodology in Management Science, IE University, Madrid, Spain (2015). ▪ International M&A Expert Charterholder, Institute for Mergers, Acquisitions & Alliances (2022). ▪ Doctor of Business Administration, IE Business School, Madrid, Spain (Expected 2023).
<p>Education & Professional Affiliations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2003-05: Management Trainee, BS&T Co. Ltd (now Massy (Barbados) Ltd). ▪ 2005-10: Business Analyst, Super Centre Ltd (now Massy Stores (Barbados) Ltd). ▪ 2010-14: Regional Business Development Analyst, Neal & Massy Food Group. ▪ 2014-18: Regional Strategy & Business Development Manager, Massy Integrated Retail BU. ▪ 2019-20: Director, Strategy & Business Development, Massy Group. ▪ 2020-21: VP, Corporate Strategy & Business Development, Massy Group. ▪ 2021-22: VP, Corporate Strategy & Transactions, Massy Group. ▪ 2023-Present: Senior VP, Corporate Strategy & Transactions, Massy Group.
<p>Career Progression & Executive Footprint</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Boards: Massy Ltd, Massy (Barbados) Ltd, Massy Integrated Retail Portfolio, Massy Properties (Barbados) Ltd (Chair), Massy Energy (Barbados) Ltd, Massy International Limited, Massy Finance (Barbados) Ltd, Massy Barbados Defined Contribution Pension Plan (Chair), BS&T Pension Scheme, UWI Sagikor Cave Hill School of Business & Management
<p>Key Skills</p>	<p>Strategic Planning, M&A & Divestiture Execution, Business & Financial Analysis, Market Research, New Business Development, Program Management, Executive Management, Corporate Office Administration</p>
<p>Personal Interests</p>	<p>Science Fiction, Business Research, Global Current Affairs, Travelling</p>

Source: Compiled by author